

Revised checklist of weevils (Coleoptera: Curculionoidea excluding Scolytidae and Platypodidae) from Siberia and the Russian Far East

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Abstract

Currently, 1464 species of Curculionid beetles (Nemonychidae – 1, Anthribidae – 76, Rhynchitidae – 78, Attelebidae – 28, Brentidae – 131 and Curculionidae – 1150) are recorded from Siberia and the Russian Far East. Forty species are found in Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Okrug, 84 species in Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug, 313 species in Tyumen Oblast, 182 species in Chelyabinsk Oblast, 129 species in Kurgan Oblast, 172 species in Omsk Oblast, 299 species in Tomsk Oblast, 439 species in Novosibirsk Oblast, 324 species in Kemerovo Oblast, 356 species in Altay Krai, 296 species in Altai Republic, 182 species in Krasnoyarsk Krai, 114 species in Republic of Khakassia, 244 species in Tyva Republic, 283 species in Irkutsk Oblast, 239 species in Buryatiya Republic, 286 species in Zabaikalskii Krai, 153 species in Sakha (Yakutia) Republic, 74 species in Far East: Kamchatka Oblast, 43 species in Chukotka Autonomous Okrug, 105 species in Magadan Oblast, 325 species in Amur Oblast, 312 species in Khabarovsk Krai, 599 species in Primorsky Krai, 225 species in Sakhalin Is. and 218 species in Kuriles Isl. 112 species are excluded from the fauna of Siberia and the Russian Far East. New synonyms, *Trichosmobodes* L. Arnoldi, 1975, **syn. nov.** to *Holomrasus* Reitter, 1912, *Notaris illibata*

Faust, 1882, **syn. nov.** to *N. acridulus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Larinus ruber* Motschulsky, 1845, **syn. nov.** to *L. impressus* Gebler, 1829, *Lixus maculatus* Roelofs, 1873, **syn. nov.** to *L. fasciculatus* Boheman, 1835, *Stephanocleonus jakovlevi* Faust, 1893, **syn. nov.** and *S. jennisseicus* Ter-Minassian, 1978, **syn. nov.** to *S. leucopterus* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1823), *Curculio budjumkanensis* Legalov, 2007, **syn. nov.** to *C. betulae* (Stephens, 1831), *Curculio parasiticus* Morimoto, 1962, **syn. nov.** to *Archarius salicivorus* (Paykull, 1792), *Otiorhynchus buchtarmensis* Bajtenov, 1977, **syn. nov.** and *O. rhododendroni* Bajtenov, 1977, **syn. nov.** to *O. grandineus* Germar, 1823, *O. perplexus* Gyllenhal, 1834, **syn. nov.** to *O. obscurus* Gyllenhal, 1834, *Tanymecus argentatus* Gyllenhal, 1840, **syn. nov.** to *Megamecus bidentatus* (Gebler, 1829), **comb. nov.** are established.

Keywords

Beetles, weevils, fauna, distribution, North Asia, Russia, biodiversity

Introduction

The superfamily Curculionoidea is the most diverse group of Coleoptera. They are widespread and have an important role in ecosystems. The first review on the fauna of the studied area was given by Heyden (1880–1881). In 2010, the author (Legalov 2010a) published a list of Curculionoidea from Asian Russia. Many new articles were published and new materials were studied over the past 10 years. This study provides a revised and corrected checklist of Curculionoidea (except Scolytidae and Platypodidae) from Siberia and the Russian Far East.

The presented work is the result of many years of research by the author (Akulov et al. 2014; Borisova et al. 2014; Borovec and Legalov 2004; Caldara and Legalov 2016; Chabanenko and Legalov 2008; Efimov and Legalov 2011, 2012; Galich and Legalov 2012; Galich et al. 2016; Gurina et al. 2016, 2018, 2019a, 2019b; Korotyaev and Legalov 2002; Krivets and Legalov 2002; Legalov 1994, 1995, 1996a, 1996b, 1997a, 1997b, 1997c, 1997d, 1998a, 1998b, 1998c, 1999a, 1999b, 1999c, 1999d, 1999e, 2000a, 2000b, 2000c, 2001a, 2001c, 2001d, 2001e, 2001f, 2002a, 2002b, 2002c, 2003a, 2003b, 2004a, 2004b, 2004c, 2004d, 2005a, 2005b, 2005c, 2006a, 2006b, 2006c, 2006d, 2006e, 2006f, 2007a, 2007b, 2008, 2009a, 2009b, 2009c, 2009d, 2009e, 2009f, 2009g, 2009h, 2009i, 2009j, 2010a, 2010b, 2011a, 2011b, 2011c, 2011d, 2011e, 2011f, 2012a, 2012b, 2012c, 2013a, 2017a, 2017b, 2017c, 2018b, 2019, 2020a, 2020b; Legalov and Borisova 2011; Legalov and Dudko 2006; Legalov and Efimov 2007; Legalov and Korsun 2004; Legalov and Legalova 2005; Legalov et al. 2006a, 2006b, 2006c, 2007, 2009; Legalov and Opanassenko 1992, 1996, 2000; Legalov and Poiras 2006; Legalov and Reshetnikov 2018, 2020a, 2020b; Legalov and Sergeev 2018; Legalov and Shevnin 2007a, 2007b; Legalov and Sitnikov 2000; Legalov and Streltsov 2005; Legalov and Zinchenko 2018; Legalov et al. 2015, 2016; Opanassenko and Legalov 1992, 1996; Tshernyshev and Legalov 2008; Zinovyev et al. 2016) of Curculionoidea from Siberia and the Russian Far East.

Material and methods

The studied materials are deposited in the Institute of Systematics and Ecology of Animals (Novosibirsk), Zoological Institute (St. Petersburg), Zoological Museum of Moscow State University (Moscow), Institute of Biology and Soil Science (Vladivostok), Staatliches Museum für Tierkunde (Dresden) and some private collections.

All published records of weevils from Siberia and Russian Far East (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017; Anderson 1997; Arnoldi 1975; Arnoldi et al., 1974; Arzanov 2005, 2006a, 2006b; Atlas ...; Averensky 2003a, 2003b; Babenko and Krivets 1981; Babenko 1982; Bajtenov 1974, 1977a, 1977b, 1980, 1981; Barrios 1984, 1986; Barrios and Egorov 1987, 1988; Berlov and Tomilova 1980; Bessolitsyna and Shilenkov 1980; Bukhhalo et al. 2011, 2014; Caldara 1979, 1985, 1986, 1990, 2007, 2008; Caldara and O'Brien 1995; Chabanenko 2007a, 2007b; Cherepanov and Opanassenko 1963; Colonnelli 1986, 2004; Csiki 1934a, 1934b, 1936; Dalla Torre et al. 1932, 1936, 1937; Dalla Torre and Hustache 1930; Dalla Torre and Schenkling 1932; Dalla Torre and Voss 1930, 1937; Dieckmann 1968, 1972, 1973, 1977, 1980a, 1980b, 1983, 1986, 1988; Efimov 2015; Filimonov 2012; Egorov and Korotyaev 1974, 1976, 1986; Egorov and Kabakov 1976; Egorov 1976a, 1976b, 1976c, 1977, 1979a, 1979b, 1981, 1988, 1989, 1992, 1996a, 1996b, 1996c, 1996d, 1996e, 1996f; Egorov and Basarukina 1981; Egorov and Berezhnykh 1987; Egorov and Zherichin 1996; Egorov et al. 1996; Emden and Emden 1939; Folwaczny 1973; Fremuth 1982; Frieser 1981; Gratshev 2015; Günter and Zumpt 1933; Heyden 1880–1881, 1893; Hong and Korotyaev 2002; Hustache 1934, 1936, 1938; Ismailova 1993, 2006; Khruleva and Korotyaev 1999, 2012; Klima 1934a, 1934b, 1934c, 1935; Kojima and Morimoto 1994; Korotyaev 1976a, 1976b, 1976c, 1976d, 1977a, 1979, 1980a, 1980b, 1981, 1984a, 1984b, 1988, 1990, 1992a, 1992b, 1995a, 1995b, 1996, 1997a, 1997b, 1997c, 1999a, 1999b, 2006, 2008, 2016, 2017; Korotyaev and Ter-Minassian, 1977; Korotyaev and Egorov 1977, 1995; Korotyaev and Cholokava 1989; Korotyaev and Sofronova 2016; Korotyaev et al. 1993; Korotyaev and Krivets, 1996; Korotyaev and Hong, 2004; Korshunov 1973; Košťál and Caldara 2019; Krivets 1979, 1980, 1981, 1983, 1984, 1997; Krivets and Korotyaev, 1998; Krivolutskaja 1961; Krivolutskaja et al. 1978; Kuzmina and Korotyaev 2019; Lavrov 1927; Lona 1936, 1937, 1938; Lukjanovich and Ter-Minassian 1955; Mit'kova and Opanassenko 1988; Morimoto 1959, 1960, 1962a, 1962b, 1978, 1979, 1980, 1981, 1982, 1984, 1986, 1987a, 1987b, 1988, 2000; Morimoto and Lee, 1993; Morimoto and Miyakawa 1995; Prena et al. 2014; O'Brien et al. 1994; Olshvang and Bogacheva 1990; Opanassenko 1970, 1972, 1973, 1974, 1976a, 1976b, 1978a, 1978b, 1984, 1986a, 1986b, 1987, 1990; Nogovitsyna and Shilenkov, 2003; Pelsue and Zhang 2000; Perrin and Meregalli 2007; Schenkling and Marshall 1929, 1931, 1934; Samoilov 1936; Schenkling 1935; Sergeeva and Dedyukhin 2018, 2019, 2020; Shilenkov and Korotyaev 2020; Takenouchi et al. 1970; Ter-Minassian 1936, 1948, 1953, 1956, 1979, 1984, 1988; Thompson 2005, 2006; Tomilova 1962; Zabaluev 2016; Zaslavskij 1956; 1961; Zherichin 1972,

Figure 1. Map of the administrative units of studied area.

1981, 1997; Zherichin and Nazarov 1990; Zherichin and Egorov 1991; Yoshihara and Morimoto, 1994; Voss 1955, 1958; Voss and Chujo 1960; Wagner 1910, 1930; Wanat 1995; Winkler 1930–1932 etc.) are included.

The systematics of studied taxa are from Legalov’s works (Gratshev and Legalov 2014; Legalov 2015, 2017a, 2017b, 2017c, 2018a, 2018c, 2018d, 2020a, 2020b, 2020c, 2020d).

The species or data which are not checked by the author are listed in quotation marks. Species excluded from the fauna of Siberia and Russian Far East are shown in square brackets. Abbreviations for the names of federal subjects are follow (Fig. 1):

West Siberia: Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Okrug – YAN, Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug – KHM, Tyumen Oblast – TMN, Chelyabinsk Oblast (part of West Siberian Plain) – CHEL, Kurgan Oblast – KURG, Omsk Oblast – OMS, Tomsk Oblast – TOM, Novosibirsk Oblast – NOV, Kemerovo Oblast – KEM, Altay Krai – ALT, Altai Republic – RAL, Krasnoyarsk Krai – KRN, Republic of Khakassia – KHA, Tyva Republic – TUV;

East Siberia: Irkutsk Oblast – IRK, Buryatiya Republic – BUR, Zabaikalskii Krai (formerly Chita Oblast) – CHT, Sakha (Yakutia) Republic – YAK;

Far East: Kamchatka Oblast – KAM, Chukotka Autonomous Okrug – CHUK, Magadan Oblast – MAG, Amur Oblast – AMUR, Khabarovsk Krai – KHAB, Primorsky Krai – PRIM, Sakhalin Is. – SAKH, Kuriles Isl. – KUR.

Results

Superfamily Curculionoidea Latreille, 1802

Family Nemonychidae Bedel, 1882

Subfamily Cimberidinae Gozis, 1882

Tribe Cimberidini Gozis, 1882

Genus *Cimberis* des Gozis, 1881

attelaboides (Fabricius, 1787) – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, CHT, AMUR.

Family Anthribidae Billberg, 1820

Subfamily Urodontinae Thomson, 1859

Genus *Bruchela* Dejan, 1821

kaszabi (Strejcek, 1973) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, NOV, ALT, KEM, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT.

suturalis (Fabricius, 1792) – KURG.

Subfamily Anthribinae Billberg, 1820

Tribe Cratoparini LeConte, 1876

Genus *Euparius* Schoenherr, 1823

koltzei (Reitter, 1895) – PRIM.

Tribe Anthribini Billberg, 1820

= Trigonorhinini Valentine, 1999

Genus *Anthribus* Geoffroy, 1762

[*fasciatus* Forster, 1770 – records of this species from “BUR, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM” (Egorov 1996c) are wrong].

kuwanai (Yuasa, 1931) – “KHAB, PRIM, SAKH” (Egorov 1996c).

nebulosus Forster, 1770 – KHM, TOM, NOV, ALT, KRN, TUV, IRK, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

niveovariegatus (Roelofs, 1879) – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

scapularis (Gebler, 1833) – NOV, ALT, IRK, BUR, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Opanthribus* Schilsky, 1907

tessellatus (Boheman, 1829) – IRK, BUR, CHT, MAG, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Trigonorhinus* Wollaston, 1861

dolgovi (Korotyaev, 1977) – ALT, KRN, KHA, TUV, BUR, CHT.

Tribe Ozotomerini Morimoto, 1972

Genus *Ozotomerus* Perroud, 1853

japonicus japonicus Sharp, 1891 – SAKH.
japonicus laferi Egorov, 1986 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Tribe Basitropini Lacordaire, 1866

Genus *Basitropis* Jekel, 1855

nitidicutis nitidicutis Jekel, 1855 – “KUR” (Egorov 1996c).

Tribe Platystomini Pierce, 1916

Genus *Platystomos* Schneider, 1791

albinus (Fabricius, 1758) – TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, CHT, YAK, CHUK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
sellatus sellatus (Roelofs, 1879) – “KUR” (Egorov 1996c).

Genus *Penestica* Pascoe, 1859

brevis albescens Shibata, 1963 – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996c).

Tribe Ecelonerini Lacordaire, 1866

Genus *Eucorynus* Schoenherr, 1823

[*crassicornis* (Fabricius, 1801) – “Eastern Siberia, Far East” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Tribe Apolectini Lacordaire, 1866

Genus *Apolecta* Pascoe, 1859

lewisii Sharp, 1891 – “KUR” (Egorov 1996c).

Tribe Mycterini Morimoto, 1972

Genus *Sympaector* Kirsch, 1875

rugirostris (Sharp, 1891) – KUR.
ussuriensis Egorov, 1996 – PRIM.

Tribe Tropiderini Lacordaire, 1866

Genus *Acorynus* Schoenherr, 1833

asanoi (Nakane, 1963) – “SAKH (?)” (Egorov 1996c).
latirostris (Sharp, 1891) – KHAB, PRIM.
poecilus Shibata, 1963 – “SAKH (?)” (Egorov 1996c).

Genus *Agonotropis* Egorov, 1988*terminassianae* Egorov, 1988 – PRIM.**Genus *Androceras* Jordan, 1928***flavellicornis* (Sharp, 1891) – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996c).**Genus *Basarukinia* Egorov, 1996***insignis* (Morimoto, 1980) – “Khab, PRIM, SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1996c).**Genus *Gonotropis* LeConte, 1876***crassirostris* (Sharp, 1891) – IRK, BUR, CHT, CHUK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.*dorsalis* (Gyllenhal, 1813) – KURG, TMN, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, CHUK.**Genus *Nessiadocus* Heller, 1925***repandus repandus* (Jordan, 1912) – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996c).*triodes* (Jordan, 1912) – “KUR” (Egorov 1996c).**Genus *Sphinctotropis* Kolbe, 1895***laxa* (Sharp, 1891) – PRIM.**Genus *Tropideres* Schoenherr, 1823***albistrostris* (Schaller 1783) – TOM, NOV, ALT.*cyaneotegrum* Oda, 1979 – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996c).*insularis* Shibata, 1963 – “KUR (?)” (Egorov 1996c).*japonicus japonicus* (Roelofs, 1879) – “PRIM” (Egorov 1996c).*naevulus* Faust, 1887 – YAK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, KUR.*roelofsi roelofsi* (Lewis, 1879) – “PRIM” (Egorov 1996c).*securus* (Boheman, 1839) – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996c).**Tribe Allandrini Pierce, 1930****Genus *Allandrus* LeConte, 1876***iriei* Morimoto, 1980 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.*undulatus* (Panzer, 1795) – NOV, CHT.**Genus *Enedreytes* Schoenherr, 1839***gotoi* Shibata, 1969 – PRIM.**Genus *Phaeochrotes* Pascoe, 1860***pudens* (Gyllenhal, 1833) – “Far East” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

Tribe Zygaenodini Lacordaire, 1866

= Platyrhinini Bedel, 1882

Genus *Aphaulimia* Morimoto, 1972

debilis (Sharp, 1891) – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1996c).

Genus *Autotropis* Jordan, 1924

basipennis (Sharp, 1891) – PRIM.

distinguenda (Sharp, 1891) – PRIM.

montana montana Wolfrum, 1948 – “Far East” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

montana sibirica Frieser, 1981 – “E Siberia” (Frieser 1981).

Genus *Dissoleucas* Jordan, 1925

niveirostris (Fabricius, 1798) – NOV, KEM, ALT, IRK, BUR, CHT.

Genus *Exechesops* Schoenherr, 1847

foliates Frieser, 1995 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

[*leucopis* (Jordan, 1928) – “Far East” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Genus *Gibber* Jordan, 1895

brevirostris (Sharp, 1891) – KHAB, PRIM.

incisus (Sharp, 1891) – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996c).

nodulosus (Sharp, 1891) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Habrissus* Pascoe, 1859

cylindricus (Sharp, 1891) – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996c).

formosanus Jordan, 1912 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

longipes (Sharp, 1891) – “PRIM” (Egorov 1996c).

pardalis (Sharp, 1891) – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1996c).

Genus *Oxyderes* Jordan, 1928

fastigatus (Jordan, 1924) – “PRIM” (Egorov 1996c).

Genus *Phaulimia* Pascoe, 1859

aberrans (Sharp, 1891) – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996c).

confines (Sharp, 1891) – “PRIM” (Egorov 1996c).

Genus *Platyrhinus* Clairville, 1798

resinosus (Scopoli, 1763) – CHEL, TMN, OMS, NOV, ALT, IRK.

Genus *Rhaphitropis* Reitter, 1916

guttifer guttifer (Sharp, 1891) – AMUR, PRIM, SAKH.

japonica Shibata, 1978 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

marchica (Herbst, 1797) – RAL, CHT.

nigromaculata Morimoto, 1981 – PRIM, “SAKH (?)” (Egorov 1996c).

truncatoides Morimoto, 1981 – PRIM, “SAKH” (Egorov 1996c).

Genus *Ulorhinus* Sharp, 1891

funebrus Sharp, 1891 – PRIM, “SAKH” (Egorov 1996c).

gokani Morimoto, 1981 – “KUR” (Egorov 1996c).

Genus *Uncifer* Jordan, 1904

akashii Morimoto, 1981 – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996c).

difficilis (Sharp, 1891) – PRIM.

pectoralis (Sharp, 1891) – “PRIM, SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1996c).

truncatus (Sharp, 1891) – PRIM, SAKH.

Subfamily Choraginae Kirby, 1819**Tribe Valenfriesiini Alonso-Zarazaga et Lyal, 1999****Genus *Valenfriesia* Alonso-Zarazaga et Lyal, 1999**

wollastoni (Sharp, 1891) – KUR.

Tribe Araecerini Lacordaire, 1866**Genus *Deropygus* Sharp, 1891**

histrion Sharp, 1891 – PRIM.

Genus *Xanthoderopygus* Senoh, 1984

flavicollis (Morimoto, 1978) – PRIM, KUR.

jocosus (Sharp, 1891) – AMUR.

Tribe Choragini Kirby, 1819**Genus *Choragus* Kirby, 1819**

anobioides Sharp, 1891 – PRIM, KUR.

cissoids Sharp, 1891 – “KUR” (Egorov 1996c).

cryphaloides Sharp, 1891 – SAKH, KUR.

cryptocephalus Sharp, 1891 – SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Citocalus* Johraku, 1953

pygidialis Johraku, 1953 – AMUR.

Family Rhynchitidae Gistel, 1848

Subfamily Rhynchitinae Gistel, 1856

Supertribe Rhynchititae Gistel, 1848

Tribe Auletini Desbrochers des Loges, 1908

Subtribe Auletorhinina Voss, 1935

=Auletobiina Legalov, 2001

Genus *Auletobius* Desbrochers des Loges, 1869

Subgenus *Auletobius* s. str.

puberulus (Faust, 1882) – PRIM.

irkutensis Faust, 1893 – IRK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

egorovi Legalov, 2006 – PRIM.

sanguisorbae (Schrank, 1798) – TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Subgenus *Pseudometopum* Legalov, 2003

submaculatus (Sharp, 1889) – “PRIM, SAKH” (Egorov 1996d).

Subtribe Pseudomesauletina Legalov, 2001

Genus *Eurostauletes* Voss, 1933

longimanus (Gebler, 1829) – ALT, RAL, TUV, CHT, KAM, MAG.

Genus *Pseudomesauletes* Legalov, 2003

Subgenus *Pseudomesauletes* s. str.

uniformis (Roelofs, 1875) – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1996d).

Tribe Eugnamptini Voss, 1930

Genus *Aderorhinus* Sharp, 1889

crioceroides (Roelofs, 1874) – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996d).

Genus *Eugnamptobius* Voss, 1922

flavipes (Sharp, 1889) – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1996d).

Genus *Neoeugnamptus* Legalov, 2003

amurensis (Faust, 1882) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, KUR.

Tribe Deporaini Voss, 1929

Genus *Caenorhinus* C.G. Thomson, 1859

Subgenus *Caenorhinus* s. str.

eumegacephalus (Sawada, 1993) – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996d).

megacephalus (Germar, 1823) – TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Subgenus *Flavodeporaus* Legalov, 2007

fuscipennis (Sharp, 1889) – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1996d).

vossi (Sawada, 1993) – “KUR” (Egorov 1996d).

Subgenus *Orientalodepus* Legalov, 2003

minimus koreanus (Voss, 1929) – PRIM.

Genus *Chokkirius* Kono, 1929

truncatus (Sharp, 1889) – SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Deporaus* Samouelle, 1819

Subgenus *Deporaus* s. str.

betulae (Linnaeus, 1758) – YAN, KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Subgenus *Japonodeporaus* Legalov, 2007, stat. res.

[The statuses of several Rhynchitidae and Attelabidae taxa are restored according by Legalov (2007)].

hartmanni Voss, 1929 – “KUR” (Egorov 1996d).

Subgenus *Pseudapoderites* Legalov, 2003

azarovae Legalov, 2006 – SAKH.

pacatus (Faust, 1882) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

septentrionalis Sawada, 1993 – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1996d).

Subgenus *Roelofsidedeporaus* Legalov, 2003

affectatus Faust, 1887 – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

nidificus Sawada et Lee, 1986 – “KUR” (Egorov 1996d).

unicolor (Roelofs, 1875) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Eusproda* Sawada, 1987

proxima (Faust, 1882) – IRK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, KUR.

Genus *Paleodeporaus* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.

rhynchitoides (Sawada, 1993) – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996d).

ussuriensis (Legalov, 2006) – PRIM.

Genus *Paradeporaus* Kono, 1927

depressus (Faust, 1882) – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Tribe Rhynchitini Gistel, 1848

Subtribe Lasiorhynchitina Legalov, 2003

Genus *Lasiorhynchites* Jekel, 1860

Subgenus *Nelasiorhynchites* Legalov, 2003

brevirostris (Roelofs, 1875) – “KUR” (Egorov 1996d).

ussuriensis Legalov, 2002 – PRIM.

Subtribe Temnocerina Legalov, 2003

Genus *Neocoenorrhinus* Voss, 1952

Subgenus *Neocoenorhinidius* Legalov, 2003

interruptus (Voss, 1920) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

pauxillus (Germar, 1823) – OMS.

thomsoni (Faust, 1884) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Subgenus *Neocoenorrhinus* s. str.

germanicus (Herbst, 1797) – TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, IRK, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Temnocerus* Thunberg, 1815

Subgenus *Paratemnocerus* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.

subglaber (Desbrochers des Loges, 1897) – KURG, NOV, ALT, CHT.

Subgenus *Temnocerus* s. str.

caeruleus (Fabricius, 1798) – OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT, TUV, IRK, PRIM.

japonicus (Morimoto, 1958) – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

longiceps (C.G. Thomson, 1888) – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.

nanus (Paykull, 1792) – TMN, CHEL, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN.

rubripes (Reitter, 1916) – TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

sibiricus Legalov, 2006 – KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR.

Subtribe Rhynchitina Gistel, 1848

Genus *Cartorhynchites* Voss, 1958

Subgenus *Cartorhynchoides* Legalov, 2003

amamiensis (Voss, 1971) – “SAKH (?)” (Egorov 1996d).

apertus (Sharp, 1889) – “PRIM, SAKH” (Egorov 1996d).

subtilis (Sawada, 1993) – “SAKH (?)” (Egorov 1996d).

Genus *Cneminvolvulus* Voss, 1960**Subgenus *Cneminvolvulus* s. str.***rugosicollis* (Voss, 1920) – AMUR, PRIM.**Subgenus *Nigrorhynchites* Legalov, 2007***cornix* (Sawada, 1993) – “KUR” (Egorov 1996d).**Subgenus *Metinvovulus* Legalov, 2003***haradai* (Kono, 1940) – SAKH, KUR.*sundukovi* (Legalov, 2007) – PRIM.**Genus *Epirhynchites* Voss, 1969, stat. res.****Subgenus *Tshernyshevinius* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.***auratus* (Scopoli, 1763) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, TUV.**Subgenus *Epirhynchites* s. str.***heros* (Roelofs, 1874) – KHAB, PRIM.*zherichini* Legalov, 2004 – CHT.**Genus *Involvulus* Schrank, 1798***cupreus* (Linnaeus, 1761) – TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KR, IRK, BUR, KHAB, PRIM.*cylindricollis* (Schilsky, 1906) – SAKH, KUR.**Genus *Maculinvolvulus* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.***singularis* (Roelofs, 1874) – “KUR” (Egorov 1996d).**Genus *Opacoinvolvulus* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.***gensanensis* (Voss, 1920) – PRIM.**Genus *Parinvovulus* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.****Subgenus *Nigroinvovulus* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.***apionoides* (Sharp, 1889) – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1996d).*zherichini* (Legalov, 2004) – AMUR, PRIM.**Subgenus *Parinvovulus* s. str.***pilosus* (Roelofs, 1874) – SAKH, KUR.*placidus* (Sharp, 1889) – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1996d).

Subgenus *Parinvolvoldes* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.

ussuriensis Legalov, 2003 – PRIM.

= *legalovi* Alonso-Zarazaga, 2011

Genus *Pseudomechoris* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.

aethiops (Bach, 1854) – CHEL.

Genus *Rhynchites* Schneider, 1791

bacchus (Linnaeus, 1758) – KURG.

fulgidus Faldermann, 1835 – CHT, PRIM.

Genus *Teretriorhynchites* Voss, 1938, stat. res.

Subgenus *Aphlorhynchites* Sawada, 1993, stat. res.

amabilis (Roelofs, 1874) – NOV, KEM, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

hirticollis (Faust, 1882) – KHAB, PRIM.

pubescens (Fabricius, 1775) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.

Subgenus *Teretriorhynchites* s. str.

icosandriae ussuriensis (Voss, 1930) – BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Thompsonirhinus* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.

Subgenus *Maculinvoles* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.

mandschuricus (Voss, 1939) – PRIM.

Tribe Byctiscini Voss, 1923

Subtribe *Svetlanaebyctiscina* Legalov, 2003

Genus *Svetlanaebyctiscus* Legalov, 2001

vitis (Ter-Minassian, 1959) – PRIM.

Subtribe *Byctiscina* Voss, 1923

Genus *Aspidobyctiscus* Schilsky, 1903

Subgenus *Aspidobyctiscus* s. str.

lacunipennis (Jekel, 1860) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM [This species is absent in “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Genus *Byctiscus* C.G. Thomson, 1859

betulae (Linnaeus, 1758) – YAN, KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, IRK, CHT.

congener (Jekel, 1860) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

fausti Sharp, 1889 – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996d).

populi (Linnaeus, 1758) – YAN, KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, IRK, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

princeps princeps (Solsky, 1872) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

princeps regalis (Roelofs, 1874), **stat. res.** – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1996d).

regularis Voss, 1930 – PRIM.

rugosus (Gebler, 1829) – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

venustus (Pascoe, 1875) – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1996d).

Family Attelabidae Billberg, 1820

Subfamily Attelabinae Billberg, 1820

Tribe Euopsini Voss, 1925

Subtribe Parasynaptopsina Legalov, 2007, stat. res.

Genus *Parasynaptopsis* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.

lespedezae koreanus Voss, 1924 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

[*niger* (Kono, 1927) – records of this species from “PRIM, SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1996e) are wrong].

Genus *Parasynatops* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.

Subgenus *Parasynatops* s. str.

konoii (Sawada et Morimoto, 1985) – KUR.

Subtribe Sawadaeuopsina Legalov, 2007, stat. res.

Genus *Sawadaeuops* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.

Subgenus *Sawadaeuops* s. str.

punctatostriatus (Motschulsky, 1861) – SAKH, KUR.

Tribe Attelabini Billberg, 1820

Subtribe Attelabina Billberg, 1820

Genus *Cyrtolabus* Voss, 1925

christophi (Faust, 1884) – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Attelabus* Linnaeus, 1758

Subgenus *Attelabus* s. str.

cyanellus Voss, 1925 – TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, CHUK, KAM, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

Subtribe Phialodina Legalov, 2003, stat. res.

Genus *Phialodes* Roelofs, 1874

rufipennis Roelofs, 1874 – “KUR” (Egorov 1996e).

Subtribe Henicolabina Legalov, 2007, stat. res.

Genus *Henicolabus* Voss, 1925

giganteus (Faust, 1882) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Subfamily Apoderinae Jekel, 1860

Tribe Clitostyliini Voss, 1926, stat. res.

Subtribe Pseudophrysina Legalov, 2003, stat. res.

Genus *Maculphrysus* Legalov, 2003

Subgenus *Maculphrysus* s. str.

quadrimaculatus (Faldermann, 1835) – PRIM.

Genus *Morphocorynus* Legalov, 2003

nigricollis (Roelofs, 1874) – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996e).

Tribe Hoplapoderini Voss, 1926

Subtribe Hoplapoderina Voss, 1926

Genus *Agomadaranus* Voss, 1958

Subgenus *Agomadaranus* s. str.

pardalis (Snelle van Vollenhoven, 1865) – “KUR” (Egorov 1996e).

Genus *Hoplapoderus* Jekel, 1860

echinatoides Legalov, 2003 – PRIM.

gemmatus (Thunberg, 1784) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Paroplapoderus* Voss, 1926

Subgenus *Paroplapoderus* s. str.

fallax (Gyllenhal, 1839) – BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Subgenus *Gomadaranus* Kono, 1930

vanvolxemi (Roelofs, 1876) – “KUR” (Egorov 1996e).

Genus *Phymatapoderus* Voss, 1926

flavimanus (Motschulsky, 1860) – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

Genus *Tomapoderus* Voss, 1926*ruficollis* (Fabricius, 1781) – BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.**Tribe Apoderini Jekel, 1860****Subtribe Leptapoderina Legalov, 2003, stat. res.****Genus *Compsapoderus* Voss, 1927****Subgenus *Compsapoderus* s. str.***erythropterus* (Gmelin, 1790) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN, KHA, IRK, YAK, MAG, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.*geminus* (Sharp, 1889) – PRIM (Furugel'ma Is.), KUR.**Genus *Leptapoderus* Jekel, 1860****Subgenus *Leptapoderidius* Legalov, 2007***rubidus* (Motschulsky, 1860) – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.**Subgenus *Paraleptapoderus* Legalov, 2003***carbonicolor* (Motschulsky, 1860) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.**Subgenus *Pseudoleptapoderus* Legalov, 2003***balteatus* (Roelofs, 1874) – “KUR” (Egorov 1996e).**Subtribe Apoderina Jekel, 1860****Genus *Apoderus* Olivier, 1807****Subgenus *Apoderus* s. str.***coryli* (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, CHUK, MAG, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.**Subgenus *Konoapoderus* Legalov, 2003, stat. res.***jekelii* Roelofs, 1874 – YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.**Subtribe Cycnotrachelina Legalov, 2003, stat. res.****Genus *Cycnotrachelodes* Voss, 1955****Subgenus *Cycnotrachelodes* s. str.***cyanopterus* (Motschulsky, 1861) – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.*roelofsi* (Harold, 1877) – “SAKH” (Egorov 1996e).*ussuriensis* (Voss, 1931) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.**Genus *Paracycnotrachelus* Voss, 1924***chinensis* (Jekel, 1860) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Paratrachelophorus* Voss, 1924

Subgenus *Paratrachelophorus* s. str.

longicornis (Roelofs, 1874) – PRIM.

Family Brentidae Bilberg, 1820

Subfamily Apioninae Schoenherr, 1823

Supertribe Aspidapiitae Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

Tribe Ceratapiini Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

Genus *Diplapion* Reitter, 1916

detritum (Mulsant et Rey, 1859) – CHEL.

stolidum (Germar, 1817) – TMN, TOM, NOV, ALT.

Genus *Ceratapion* Schilsky, 1901

Subgenus *Acanephodus* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

onopordi onopordi (Kirby, 1808) – TMN, NOV, KEM, ALT, PRIM.

Subgenus *Angustapion* Wanat, 1995

decolor (Desbrochers des Loges, 1875) – NOV.

opacinum (Faust, 1887) – KEM, PRIM.

Subgenus *Ceratapion* s. str.

gibbirostre (Gyllenhal, 1813) – TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KHA, BUR, AMUR, PRIM.

kazakhstanicum (Ter-Minassian, 1969) – NOV, ALT.

secundum (Ter-Minassian, 1975) – CHT.

Genus *Omphalapion* Schilsky, 1901

buddebergi (Bedel, 1887) – TMN.

hookerorum (Kirby, 1808) – TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, KHA.

Genus *Protoceratapion* Wanat, 1995

deletum (Schilsky, 1906) – TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL.

Genus *Taphrotopium* Reitter, 1916

Subgenus *Omphatopium* Wanat, 1995

irkutense (Faust, 1888) – TOM, NOV, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR.

Subgenus *Taphrotopium* s. str.

steveni (Gyllenhal, 1839) – TMN.

sulcifrons (Herbst, 1797) – TMN, KURG, NOV, ALT.

Tribe Metapiini Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990**Genus *Metapion* Schilsky, 1906**

[*gelidum* (Faust, 1885) – record of this species from “BUR” (Bajtenov 1981) is wrong].

Tribe Kalcapiini Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990**Genus *Melanapion* Wagner, 1930****Subgenus *Melanapion* s. str.**

mandli (Schubert, 1957) – BUR, AMUR.

minimum (Herbst, 1797) – TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN, TUV, IRK, CHT, YAK, AMUR, PRIM.

naga (Nakane, 1963) – AMUR, Khab, PRIM.

Genus *Sergiola* Korotyaev, 1995**Subgenus *Golovninia* Korotyaev et Egorov, 1995**

ussuricola Korotyaev et Egorov, 1995 – Khab, PRIM.

Subgenus *Sergiola* s. str.

praecaria (Faust, 1889) – Khab, PRIM, Sakh.

rasnitsyni Korotyaev et Egorov, 1995 – PRIM.

silfverbergi (Bajtenov, 1983) – Khab, PRIM.

Genus *Squamapion* Bokor, 1923

elongatum (Germar, 1817) – TMN, ALT.

fissile (Faust, 1888) – Khab, PRIM.

flavimanum (Gyllenhal, 1833) – NOV.

lukjanovitshi (Korotyaev, 1988) – NOV, ALT.

megatoma Korotyaev, 1996 – PRIM.

samarense (Faust, 1891) – ALT, RAL, TUV.

vicinum (Kirby, 1908) – NOV.

Genus *Taenapion* Schilsky, 1906

urticarium urticarium (Herbst, 1784) – TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, PRIM, Sakh.

Tribe Aspidapiini Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990**Genus *Alocertron* Schilsky, 1901****Subgenus *Bulborhinapion* Schatzmayr, 1926**

pachyrhynchum (Gemminger, 1871) – PRIM.

Subgenus *Nearctalox* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1991

Insertae sedis

tschukotkianum (Bajtenov, 1980) – “CHUK” (Bajtenov 1980).

Genus *Aspidapion* Schilsky, 1901

Subgenus *Aspidapion* s. str.

radiolus (Marsham, 1802) – TMN, TOM, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT.

validum (Germar, 1817) – OMS, NOV, ALT.

Genus *Miniapion* Korotyaev, 1991

sulcirostre (Sharp, 1891) – SAKH, KUR.

Tribe Malvapiini Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

Genus *Pseudapion* Schilsky, 1906

fulvirostre (Gyllenhal, 1833) – ALT, “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

Supertribe Apionitae Schoenherr, 1823

Tribe Ixapiini Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

Genus *Trichopteration* Wagner, 1930

semiseriatum (Wagner, 1920) – PRIM.

Tribe Exapiini Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

Genus *Exapion* Bedel, 1887

Subgenus *Exapion* s. str.

[*compactum* (Desbrochers des Loges, 1888) – record of this species from “KURG” (Legalov 2010a) belongs to *E. difficile*].

corniculatum (Germar, 1817) – CHEL.

difficile (Herbst, 1797) – CHEL, KURG.

formaneki (Wagner, 1929) – CHEL.

Tribe Piezotrachelini Voss, 1959

Genus *Fremuthiella* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

vossi (Ter-Minassian, 1992) – CHT.

Genus *Pseudopiezotrachelus* Wagner, 1907

collaris (Schilsky, 1906) – PRIM, KUR.

placidus (Faust, 1887) – PRIM, SAKH.

Genus *Pseudoprotapion* Ehret, 1990

astragali (Paykull, 1800) – OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT, CHT, PRIM.

elegantulum (Germar, 1818) – CHEL, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, IRK.

Insertae sedis

[*androssowi* (Wagner, 1908) – record of this species from “Altai” (Wagner 1930) belongs to East-Kazakhstan Prov.].

Genus *Protapion* Schilsky, 1908

apricans (Herbst, 1797) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, KEM, NOV, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, IRK, BUR, AMUR.

assimile assimile (Kirby, 1808) – TMN.

filirostre (Kirby, 1808) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL.

fulvipes fulvipes (Foureroy, 1785) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, KEM, NOV, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, IRK, BUR, AMUR, PRIM.

gracilipes (Dietrich, 1857) – TMN, CHEL.

lesnei (Schilsky, 1906) – PRIM.

ruficrus (Germar, 1817) – TMN, CHEL.

varipes (Germar, 1817) – TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM.

Tribe Aplemonini Kissinger, 1968**Genus *Aizobius* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1991**

sedi (Germar, 1818) – CHEL, TOM, NOV, TUV.

pseudosedi (Bajtenov, 1976) – NOV, ALT, AMUR.

Genus *Perapion* Wagner, 1907**Subgenus *Eroosapion* Ehret, 1994**

lemoroi (Ch. Brisout de Barneville, 1880) – PRIM.

Subgenus *Perapion* s. str.

affine (Kirby, 1808) – TMN.

connexum (Schilsky, 1902) – CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.

curtirostre (Germar, 1817) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN, TUV, AMUR, PRIM.

= *oblongum* Gyllenhal, 1839

marchicum (Herbst, 1797) – TMN, TOM, KEM.

violaceum violaceum (Kirby, 1808) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KRN, IRK.

Genus *Pseudaplemonus* Wagner, 1930

artemisiae (F. Moravitz, 1861) – OMS, NOV, ALT.

bermani Korotyaev, 1997 – CHUK.

[*externepunctatus* (Desbrochers des Loges, 1874) – record of this species from “Sibirien” (Wagner 1910) is wrong].

martjanovi (Faust, 1891) – RAL, KRN, TUV.

Genus *Pseudoperapion* Wagner, 1930

brevirostre (Herbst, 1797) – CHEL.

Tribe Catapiini Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

Genus *Catapion* Schilsky, 1906

seniculus (Kirby, 1808) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, IRK, CHT, PRIM.

Tribe Apionini Schoenherr, 1823

Subtribe Apionina Schoenherr, 1823

Genus *Apion* Herbst, 1797

arcticum Korotyaev, 1987 – CHUK.

cruentatum Walton, 1844 – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, TUV, IRK, CHT.

rubiginosum Grill, 1893 – TMN, NOV.

Subtribe Synapiina Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

= Trichapiina Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

Genus *Isochnopterapion* Bokor, 1923

Subgenus *Chlorapion* Gyorffy, 1956

virens (Herbst, 1797) – TMN.

Subgenus *Isochnopterapion* s. str.

loti (Kirby, 1808) – TMN.

Genus *Stenopterapion* Bokor, 1923

Subgenus *Stenopterapion* s. str.

[*intermedium* (Eppelsheim, 1875) – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

meliloti (Kirby, 1808) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, KRN, KHA, IRK, PRIM.

tenuis (Kirby, 1808) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, NOV, KEM, RAL, IRK.

Genus *Synapion* Schilsky, 1902

Subgenus *Parasynapion* Legalov, 2003

alexandri Korotyaev, 1988 – TUV.

Subgenus *Synapion* s. str.

ebeninum (Kirby, 1808) – TMN, KURG.

Genus *Trichapion* Wagner, 1912

simile simile (Kirby, 1811) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, KEM, NOV, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, AMUR, PRIM.

Subtribe *Toxorhynchina* Scudder, 1893

= Oxystomatina Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

Genus *Cyanapion* Bokor, 1923**Subgenus *Bothryorrhynchapion* Bokor, 1923**

afes (Gyllenhal, 1833) – TMN, TOM, NOV, TUV.

gnarum (Faust, 1891) – NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, IRK.

gyllenhali (Kirby, 1808) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, KRN, IRK, CHT, PRIM.

platalea (Germar, 1817) – NOV, KHAB.

Subgenus *Cyanapion* s. str.

alcyoneum (Germar, 1817) – TMN, KURG, NOV, KEM.

columbinum (Germar, 1817) – TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM.

spencii (Kirby, 1808) – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, IRK.

Insertae sedis

eniseiense (Bajtenov, 1977) – “KHA” (Bajtenov 1977a).

Genus *Eutrichapion* Reitter, 1916**Subgenus *Eutrichapion* s. str.**

erwi (Kirby, 1808) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

meditabundum (Faust, 1890) – OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, IRK, TUV, CHT, YAK, AMUR, PRIM.

rectirostre (Schilsky, 1906) – TOM, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, PRIM.

viciae (Paykull, 1798) – YAN, TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Subgenus *Phalacrolobus* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

melancholicum (Wencker, 1864) – TMN, KURG, NOV.

Subgenus *Psilocalymma* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

facetum (Gyllenhal, 1839) – TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHAK, IRK.

punctigerum (Paykull, 1792) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL.
rhomboidale (Desbrochers des Loges, 1871) – NOV, KEM, KRN, KHAK, ALT, RAL.
Insertae sedis
crassiforme (Bajtenov, 1977) – “BUR” (Bajtenov 1977a).

Genus *Hemitrichapion* Voss, 1959

Subgenus *Microtinocyba* Legalov, 2001

tschernovi terektinensis Legalov, 2001 – RAL.
tschernovi tschernovi (Ter-Minassian, 1973) – YAN, KRN.
tschernovi tuvensis Legalov, 2001 – TUV.

Subgenus *Tinocyba* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

alexсандi Legalov, 2001 – RAL.
amguemae (Korotyaev, 1991) – CHUK.
korotyaevi Legalov, 2001 – RAL.
lenense (Schilsky, 1906) – YAK.
reflexum (Gyllenhal, 1833) – KURG, NOV, ALT, RAL, KHA, TUV, IRK.
romani Legalov, 2007 – RAL.
suppantschitschi Legalov, 2002 – RAL.
tschegitunensis Legalov, 2001 – CHUK.

Genus *Holotrichapion* Gyorffy, 1956

Subgenus *Apiops* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

[*pisi* (Fabricius, 1802) – record of this species from “Siberien” (Wagner 1910) is wrong].

Subgenus *Legaricapion* Ehret, 1990

aethiops (Herbst, 1797) – TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL.

Genus *Loborhynchapion* Gyorffy, 1956

amethystinum (Miller, 1875) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, NOV, ALT, KRN, IRK, YAK, CHUK.

[*lobirostre* (Reitter, 1901) – record of this species from “Altai” (Bajtenov 1977b) belongs to East-Kazakhstan Prov.].

Genus *Mesotrichapion* Gyorffy, 1956

dauricum (Faust, 1888) – CHT.
dudkorum Legalov, 1997 – RAL.
punctirostre (Gyllenhal, 1839) – OMS, TOM, NOV, ALT, KHA.
wrangelianum (Korotyaev, 1977) – CHUK.

Genus *Oxystoma* Dumeril, 1806*abruptum* (Sharp, 1891) – PRIM.*cerdo* (Gerstaecker, 1854) – YAN, TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHAK, TUV, IRK, BUR, AMUR, PRIM, SAKH.*opeticum* (Bach, 1854) – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN.*pomonae* (Fabricius, 1798) – “Sibirien” (Wagner 1910).*subulatum* (Kirby, 1808) – TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, CHT, AMUR, PRIM.**Genus *Tatyanapion* Legalov, 1997***laticeps* (Desbrochers des Loges, 1870) – TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.**Subfamily Nanophyinae Gistel, 1856****Tribe Corimaliini Alonso-Zarazaga, 1989****Genus *Corimalia* des Gozis, 1885***aliena* (Faust, 1890) – TUV.*reaumuriae* (Zherikhin, 1984) – TUV.**Genus *Hypophyes* Reitter, 1916****Subgenus *Hypophyes* s. str.***hyalinus* (Zherichin, 1972) – NOV.**Tribe Nanophyini Gistel, 1856****Genus *Alonsiellus* Zherichin, 1996***pubescens* (Roelofs, 1875) – PRIM.**Genus *Dieckmanniellus* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1989***nitidulus* (Gyllenhal, 1838) – NOV, TUV.**Genus *Pericartiellus* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1989***telephii* (Bedel, 1900) – OMS, NOV, ALT.*zinovjevi* (Zherichin, 1981) – AMUR.**Genus *Microon* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1989***sahlbergi* (C.R. Sahlberg, 1835) – TMN, OMS, ALT.**Genus *Nanomimus* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1989***borisi* Zherichin, 1996 – PRIM.*circumscriptus* (Aube, 1864) – TMN.

hemisphaericus (Olivier, 1807) – TMN.

suturalis (Pic, 1907) – PRIM, SAKH.

Genus *Nanophyes* Schoenherr, 1838

brevis obscurus Zherichin, 1982 – PRIM.

globiformis Kiesenwetter, 1864 – PRIM.

japonicus Roelofs, 1874 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

marmoratus marmoratus (Goeze, 1777) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN.

marmoratus miguelangeli Zherichin, 1996 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Subfamily Brentinae Billberg, 1820

Tribe Brentini Billberg, 1820

Subtribe Arrhenodina Lacordaire, 1866

Genus *Baryrhynchus* Lacordaire, 1866

Subgenus *Eupsalomimus* Kleine, 1916

poweri Roelofs, 1879 – “KUR” (Egorov 1996f).

Genus *Pseudorychodes* Senna, 1894

insignis (Lewis, 1883) – “PRIM” (Egorov 1996f).

Family Curculionidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily Eirrhiniinae Schoenherr, 1825

Tribe Eirrhiniini Schoenherr, 1826

Genus *Grypus* Germar, 1817

equiseti (Fabricius, 1775) – YAN, KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KHA, KRN, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

mannerheimi Faust, 1881 – CHT, YAK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Lepidonotaris* Zumpt, 1929

petax (C. Sahlberg, 1823) – CHEL, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT, CHT.

Genus *Notaris* Germar, 1817

acridulus (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, KURG, KEM, RAL, KRN, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

=*illibata* Faust, 1882, **syn. nov.** [The type of *N. illibata* from Staatliches Museum für Tierkunde (Dresden) and materials from Siberia and the Far East are studied. These specimens do not have significantly different from *N. acridulus* and belong to the same species].

aethiops (Paykull, 1792) – YAN, KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, YAK, CHUK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

altaica Legalov, 1997, **stat.res.** – KEM, RAL.

daurica Faust, 1882 – BUR, CHT.

[*discretus* Faust, 1882 – record of this species from “Siberia” (Heyden 1880-1881) belongs to East-Kazakhstan Prov.].

[*distans* Faust, 1890 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

eversmanni Faust, 1882 – CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

oryzae (Ishida, 1902) – KHAB, PRIM.

scirpi mandschurica Voss, 1940 – KHAB, PRIM.

scirpi scirpi (Fabricius, 1792) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN, TUV.

Genus *Procas* Stephens, 1831

biguttatus Faust, 1882 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Insertae sedis

sibiricus Pic, 1904 – “Sib.or.” (Thompson 2006).

Genus *Thryogenes* Bedel, 1884

festucae (Herbst, 1795) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, NOV, ALT.

fiorii Zumpt, 1928 – TMN.

neris (Paykull, 1800) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN, BUR, YAK, KAM, AMUR, KHAB.

scirrhosus (Gyllenhal, 1836) – CHEL.

ussurensis Egorov, 1979 – KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Tournotaris* Alonso-Zarazaga et Lyal, 1999

bimaculata (Fabricius, 1787) – YAN, KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, TUV, BUR, CHT, YAK, CHUK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

ochotika (Korotyaev, 1984) – BUR, YAK, CHUK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

Subtribe *Echinocnemina* Legalov, 2020

Genus *Echinocnemus* Schoenherr, 1843

squameus (Boheman, 1835) – KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Icaris* Tournier, 1874

sparganii pertinax Gyllenhal, 1835 – TMN, NOV, IRK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Subtribe Dorytomini Bedel, 1886

Genus *Dorytomus* Germar, 1817

amurensis Korotyaev, 1979 – AMUR, PRIM.

annae Korotyaev, 1976 – CHT, KAM, MAG, PRIM.

artjuchovi Korotyaev, 1976 – IRK, BUR, MAG, KAM, KHAB, PRIM.

[*caspicus* Zumpt, 1933 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

chinensis (Faust, 1883) – PRIM.

cinereus Hochhut, 1851 – KEM, IRK, CHT, MAG, AMUR, PRIM.

dejeani Faust, 1882 – TOM, “Salair” (Heyden 1880-1881).

dorsalis (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, IRK.

edoughensis Desbrochers des Loges, 1875 – YAN, KHM, TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, ALT, KRN, IRK.

egorovi Korotyaev, 1976 – MAG, PRIM.

friebi Zumpt, 1933 – KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

hirtipennis Bedel, 1884 – TMN, TOM.

ictor (Herbst, 1795) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, “E Siberia to Sakhalin” (Dieckmann 1986).

imbecillus Faust, 1883 – KHM, KRN, IRK, CHT, YAK, CHUK, KAM, MAG, PRIM.

inexpectatus Korotyaev, 1976 – MAG, PRIM.

kerzhneri Korotyaev et Egorov, 1974 – MAG, PRIM.

leucophyllus (Motschulsky, 1845) – TOM, KEM, KRN, CHUK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

longimanus (Forster, 1771) – TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, IRK, CHT.

maculipennis Roelofs, 1874 – KUR.

=*budarini* Korotyaev, 1976

majalis (Paykull, 1792) – “OMS (?)” (Lavrov 1927).

malachovi Korotyaev, 1976 – KEM, IRK, BUR, YAK, CHUK, KAM, MAG, AMUR.

minutus (Gyllenhal, 1835) – TMN, TOM, NOV, ALT.

mishka Korotyaev, 1976 – MAG, KAM, AMUR, PRIM.

nebulosus (Gyllenhal, 1835) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, TUV, IRK, PRIM.

neglectus Korotyaev, 1996 – CHUK, MAG.

nordenskioldi Faust, 1883 – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, KRN, IRK, CHT, KAM, AMUR, PRIM, SAKH.

notaroides Kono, 1930 – SAKH.

occalescens Gyllenhal, 1835 – IRK, MAG, AMUR, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

peneckeii Zumpt, 1933 – NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, AMUR, PRIM.

rectinasus Morimoto et Enda, 1962 – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

rectirostris Morimoto et Enda, 1963 – PRIM.

roelofsi Faust, 1883 – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

ruber Faust, 1895 – YAK, CHUK, KAM, MAG, KHAB, PRIM.

rubrirostris (Gravenhorst, 1807) – “Western Siberia, Eat Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

rufulus amplipennis Tournier, 1874 – RAL, TUV, YAK, CHUK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

rufulus kamtschaticus Korotyaev, 1976 – KAM.

sahlbergi Faust, 1883 – TOM.

salicinus Gyllenhal, 1827 – KURG, TOM, NOV, TUV, IRK.

subcinctus (Faust, 1883) – ALT, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

suratus (Gyllenhal, 1835) – TMN, NOV, KEM, ALT, IRK.

svorovi Reitter, 1911 – RAL, TUV, IRK, CHT, CHUK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, PRIM.

taeniatus (Fabricius, 1781) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, IRK, PRIM.

tortrix (Linnaeus, 1760) – TMN, CHEL.

tremulae (Fabricius, 1787) – TMN.

turkestanicus Formanek, 1912 – RAL.

urakoe Morimoto et Enda, 1962 – “SAKH (?)” (Egorov et al. 1996).

ussuricus Korotyaev, 1996 – PRIM.

winteri Korotyaev, 1976 – BUR, YAK, KAM, MAG.

zinovjevi Korotyaev, 1976 – AMUR.

Tribe Tanysphyrini Gistel, 1856

Genus *Tanysphyrus* Germar, 1817

Subgenus *Tanysphyroides* Egorov, 1996

brevipennis Voss, 1953 – PRIM.

=*ussuriensis* Egorov, 1996

khancaensis Egorov, 1996 – PRIM.

major Roelofs, 1874 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Subgenus *Tanysphyrus* s. str.

lemnae (Paykull, 1792) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, ALT, CHT.

Tribe Himasthlophallini Zherichin, 1991

Genus *Himasthlophallus* Egorov et Zherichin, 1991

flagellifer Egorov et Zherichin, 1991 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Tribe Bagoinini Thomson, 1859

Genus *Bagous* Germar, 1817

Subgenus *Bagous* s. str.

amurensis Egorov et Gratshev, 1990 – AMUR, PRIM.

binodulus (Herbst, 1795) – TMN, KURG, TOM.

bipunctatus (Kono, 1934) – “KHAB, PRIM” (Caldara and O'Brien 1995).

glabrirostris (Herbst, 1795) – KURG, TMN, ALT.

gracilis Egorov et Gratshev, 1990 – PRIM.

kagiashi Chujo et Morimoto, 1959 – “PRIM” (Egorov 1976b; Caldara and O'Brien 1995).

lutulentus (Gyllenhal, 1813) – KHM, TMN, NOV, KEM, ALT, KHA, KRN, IRK.
=*nigritarsis* Thomson, 1865

picturatus Egorov et Gratshev, 1990 – PRIM.

puncticollis Boheman, 1845 – TMN, TOM.

robustus Ch. Brisout de Barneville, 1863 – TMN.

subcarinatus Gyllenhal, 1836 – CHEL.

Insertae sedis

inquinamentus Gyllenhal, 1835 – “Altai” (Heyden 1880-1881).

tophyosus Gyllenhal, 1836 – “ALT, AMUR, PRIM” (Heyden 1880-1881; Egorov 1976b).

Subgenus *Macropelmus* Dejean, 1821

aliciae Cmoluch, 1983 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

argillaceus Gyllenhal, 1836 – CHEL, NOV, KEM.

frit (Herbst, 1795) – KHM, TMN, KRN.

friwaldszkyi Tournier, 1874 – TMN.

interpositus Hartmann, 1899 – AMUR, PRIM.

limosus (Gyllenhal, 1827) – KHM, TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KRN, IRK, YAK.

longitarsis Thomson, 1868 – NOV, CHT.

lutosus (Gyllenhal, 1813) – KHM, KURG, TOM.

nodulosus Gyllenhal, 1836 – KHM, TMN, ALT.

poophagoides Egorov et Gratshev, 1990 – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

rufipennis Egorov et Gratshev, 1990 – KRN, YAK, KAM, AMUR.

sulcicollis Hartmann, 1899 – PRIM.

temprestivus (Herbst, 1795) – NOV, BUR.

tarsus Egorov et Gratshev, 1990 – BUR, AMUR, PRIM.

tubulus Caldara et O’Brein, 1994 – CHEL, NOV, IRK.

Genus *Hydronomus* Schoenherr, 1825

alismatis (Marshall, 1802) – TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, ALT, KEM, AMUR, PRIM.

Tribe Raymondionimini Reitter, 1913

Genus *Alaocybites* Gilbert, 1956

dubatolovi Legalov, 2020 – KHAB.

egorovi Grebennikov, 2010 – PRIM.

Subfamily Molytinae Schoenherr, 1823

Tribe Hylobiini Kirby, 1837

Subtribe Hylobiina Kirby, 1837

Genus *Hylobius* Germar, 1817

Subgenus *Callirus* Dejean, 1821

abietis (Linnaeus, 1758) – YAN, KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB.

futabae (Morimoto, 1982) – KUR.

gebleri gebleri (Boheman, 1834) – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, CHT, AMUR, Khab, PRIM.

gebleri signatipennis (Roelofs, 1873), **stat. res.** – SAKH, KUR [Specimens from these islands are distinguished by large body size].

haroldi (Faust, 1882) – Khab, PRIM, KUR.

longulus (Faust, 1882) – RAL, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, Khab, PRIM, KUR.
=*litigiosus* Faust, 1887

montanus (Kono, 1934) – “SAKH” (Egorov et al. 1996).

pinastris (Gyllenhal, 1813) – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, Khab, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

transversovittatus (Goeze, 1777) – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.

Subgenus *Hylobius* s. str.

adachii Kono, 1934 – “SAKH” (Egorov et al. 1996).

excavatus (Laicharting, 1781) – YAN, KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, CHUK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, Khab, PRIM, SAKH.

=*sedakovi* Hochhut, 1851

=*sibiricus* Egorov, 1996

ezoensis Morimoto, 1982 – “PRIM” (Egorov et al. 1996).

Genus *Pimelocerus* Lacordaire, 1863

orientalis orientalis (Motschulsky, 1866) – SAKH, KUR.

perforatus perforatus (Roelofs, 1873) – PRIM.

= *cribripennis* Matsumura et Kono, 1928

Tribe Lepyriini Kirby, 1837

Genus *Lepyrus* Germar, 1817

arctoalpinus Korotyaev, 1998 – YAN, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, YAK.

bermani Korotyaev, 2008 – MAG.

canadensis Casey, 1896 – CHUK.

capucinus (Schaller, 1783) – “Sibirien” (Csiki 1934a).

christophi Faust, 1882 – AMUR, Khab, PRIM.

costulatus Faust, 1882 – KRN, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, MAG.

flavipunctatus Zumpt, 1936 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017), “SAKH (?)” (Egorov et al. 1996).

gemellus gemellus Kirby, 1837 – CHUK, MAG, KAM, Khab, PRIM, SAKH.

japonicus Roelofs, 1873 – AMUR, Khab, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

kabaki Korotyaev, 1995 – RAL.

kozlovi Korotyaev, 1995 – RAL.

nebulosus Motschulsky, 1860 – AMUR, Khab, PRIM, SAKH.

nordenskioldi nordenskioldi Faust, 1887 – YAN, KHM, TUV, CHT, YAK, CHUK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

palustris flavidulus Zumpt, 1936 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).
palustris palustris (Scopoli, 1763) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, IRK, “S Yakutia” (Averensky 2003b).

quadrinotatus Boheman, 1842 – BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

sokolovi Korotyaev, 1998 – KEM, RAL, KRN, KHA.

staudingeri Zumpt, 1936 – BUR.

tsherenkovi Korotyaev, 1995 – BUR, CHT.

ventricosus Faust, 1882 – IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

volgensis Faust, 1882 – YAN, KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV.

Insertae sedis

elongatus Zumpt, 1936 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

gibber Faust, 1882 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

Tribe Plinthini Lacordaire, 1863

Subtribe Plinthina Lacordaire, 1863

Genus *Kurilio* Zherichin at Egorov, 1991

monachus Zherichin et Egorov, 1991 – KUR.

Tribe Pissodini Gistel, 1856

Genus *Pissodes* Germar, 1817

castaneus (DeGeer, 1775) – TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

galloisi Kono, 1928 – “PRIM” (Egorov 1976b).

gyllenhali (C.R. Sahlberg, 1834) – KHM, TOM, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

harcyniae (Herbst, 1795) – TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, CHT, BUR, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

insignatus Boheman, 1843 – KHM, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, KAM, AMUR, KHAB.

irroratus Reitter, 1899 – KRN, CHT, YAK, KAM, MAG, KHAB.

[*nemorensis* Germar, 1823 – “PRIM” (Egorov 1976b)].

obscurus Roelofs, 1873 – “KHAB, PRIM” (Egorov 1976b).

piceae (Illiger, 1807) – “BUR” (Egorov and Berezhnykh 1987).

pini pini (Linnaeus, 1758) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

piniphilus (Herbst, 1795) – TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

validirostris (C.R. Sahlberg, 1834) – TMN, TOM, NOV, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, BUR, YAK, AMUR.

Tribe Emphyastini Lacordaire, 1863

= Thalasselephatini Alonso-Zarazaga et Lyal, 1999

Genus *Emphyastes* Mannerheim, 1852

mannerheimi Egorov et Korotyaev, 1976 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Thalasselephas* Egorov et Korotyaev, 1976

major Egorov et Korotyaev, 1976 – SAKH, KUR.

maximus Zherichin, 1991 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

minor Egorov et Korotyaev, 1976 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Tribe Sthereini Hatch, 1971

Genus *Lobosoma* Zimmerman, 1964

kurilensis Zherichin, 1991 – KUR.

rausensis (Nakane, 1963) – PRIM, KUR.

Genus *Sthereus* Motschulsky, 1845

ptinoides (Germar, 1823) – KAM, MAG, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Tribe Acicnemidini Lacordaire, 1866

Genus *Acicnemis* Fairmaire, 1849

albofasciata (Ter-Minassian, 1953) – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

dorsonigrita Voss, 1941 – KUR.

Genus *Trachodes* Germar, 1823

Subgenus *Trachodes* s. str.

subfasciatus Voss, 1957 – KUR.

Tribe Magdalini Pascoe, 1870

Genus *Magdalis* Germar, 1817

Subgenus *Aika* Barrios, 1984

margaritae Barrios, 1984 – KRN, BUR, PRIM.

Subgenus *Edo* Germar, 1819

angulicollis Boheman, 1843 – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT.

ruficornis (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, SAKH, KUR.

= *chibi* Kono, 1930

Subgenus *Laemosaccidius* Smreczynski, 1972

alni Voss, 1941 – KHAB, PRIM.

Subgenus *Magdalis* s. str.

duplicata Germar, 1819 – YAN, KHM, CHEL, NOV, ALT, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

frontalis (Gyllenhal, 1827) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, SAKH.

linearis (Gyllenhal, 1827) – TMN, CHEL, NOV, RAL, KEM, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB.

[*memnonia* (Gyllenhal, 1837) – records of this species from “ALT” (Heyden 1880-1881), “Siberia” (Barrios 1986), “PRIM” (Egorov et al. 1996) are wrong].

nitida (Gyllenhal, 1827) – PRIM.

phlegmatica (Herbst, 1797) – TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR.

violacea (Linnaeus, 1758) – OMS, TOM, NOV, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

Subgenus *Odontomagdalis* Barrios, 1984

armigera (Fourcroy, 1785) – “ALT, PRIM” (Heyden 1880-1881; Barrios and Egorov 1987).

carbonaria (Linnaeus, 1758) – YAN, KHM, TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

dieckmanni Barrios et Egorov, 1987 – PRIM.

gurjevae Barrios, 1984 – PRIM.

koltzei Heyden, 1884 – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

korotyaevi Barrios et Egorov, 1987 – KHAB, PRIM.

leni Barrios et Egorov, 1987 – PRIM, KUR.

Subgenus *Panopsis* Daniel, 1903

flavicornis (Gyllenhal, 1836) – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Subgenus *Porrothus* Dejean, 1821

cerasi (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Tribe Carciliini Pierce, 1916

Genus *Carcilia* Roelofs, 1874

strigicollis Roelofs, 1874 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

tenuistriata Heller, 1941 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Tribe Mecyslobini Reitter, 1913**Genus *Alcidodes* G.A.K. Marshall, 1939***karelini* (Boheman, 1844) – ALT.**Genus *Merus* Gistel, 1857****Subgenus *Merus* s. str.***flavosignatus* (Roelofs, 1875) – PRIM.**Genus *Neomecyslobus* Pajni et Dhir, 1987****Subgenus *Nipponomerus* Morimoto et Kojima, 2007b***nigrofasciatus* (Kono, 1928) – PRIM.**Tribe Trigonocolini Lacordaire, 1866****Genus *Trigonocolus* Lacordaire, 1863***sulcatus* Roelofs, 1875 – PRIM.*tibialis* Kono, 1928 – “PRIM” (Egorov et al. 1996).**Tribe Aminyopini Voss, 1956****Genus *Niphades* Pascoe, 1871****Subgenus *Scaphostethus* Roelofs, 1873***tubericollis* Faust, 1890 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.=*verrucosus* Voss, 1932*variegatus* (Roelofs, 1875) – SAKH, KUR.=*gibbosus* Matsumura, 1911**Tribe Colobodini Voss, 1958****Genus *Acallinus* Morimoto, 1962***tuberculatus* Morimoto, 1962 – PRIM, KUR.**Genus *Colobodes* Schoenherr, 1837***matsumurai* Kono, 1932 – PRIM, KUR.*ornatus* Roelofs, 1875 – “PRIM, KUR” (Hong et al. 2000).*valbum* Roelofs, 1875 – “PRIM” (Egorov et al. 1996).**Genus *Systaltopezus* Faust, 1887***nodosus* Faust, 1887 – PRIM.

Tribe Camptorhinini Lacordaire, 1866

Genus *Camptorhinus* Schoenherr, 1826

notabilis (Walker, 1859) – PRIM.

Tribe Gasterocercini Zherichin, 1991

Genus *Gasterocercus* Laporte et Brulle, 1828

tamanukii Kono, 1932 – “PRIM” (Egorov et al. 1996).

Genus *Menectetorus* Faust, 1894

nikitskyi Zherichin, 1991 – PRIM.

Genus *Platygasterocercus* Zherichin, 1991

anufrievi Zherichin, 1991 – PRIM.

Genus *Syrotelus* Pascoe, 1874

septentrionalis (Roelofs, 1875) – KHAB, PRIM.

umbrosus (Roelofs, 1875) – SAKH, KUR.

Tribe Cryptorhynchini Schoenherr, 1826

Subtribe Cryptorhynchina Schoenherr, 1826

Genus *Coniferocryptus* Zherichin, 1991

opacus Zherichin, 1991 – KUR.

tamanukii (Kono, 1938) – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Cryptorhynchus* Illiger, 1807

Subgenus *Cryptorhynchus* s. str.

electus (Roelofs, 1875) – KHAB, PRIM, KUR.

fasciculatus (Roelofs, 1875) – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

lapathi (Linnaeus, 1758) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

nigrovariegatus (Roelofs, 1875) – “KUR” (Egorov et al. 1996).

Genus *Eucryprorrhynchus* Heller, 1929

brandti (Harold, 1881) – “PRIM” (Egorov et al. 1996).

Genus *Shirahoshizo* Morimoto, 1962

egorovi Zherichin, 1991 – PRIM.

juglandis Zherichin, 1991 – PRIM.

rufescens (Roelofs, 1775) – PRIM.
sculpturalis Zherichin, 1991 – PRIM.

Tribe Mechistocerini Morimoto, 1978

Genus *Monaulax* Roelofs, 1875

rugicollis Roelofs, 1875 – “SAKH” (Egorov et al. 1996).

Genus *Rhadinomerus* Faust, 1892

babai Morimoto, 1987 – “KUR” (Egorov et al. 1996).

Subfamily Lixinae Schoenherr, 1823

Tribe Lixini Schoenherr, 1823

= Rhinocyllini Lacordaire, 1863

Genus *Eustenopus* Petri, 1907

[*lanuginosus* (Faust, 1885) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Genus *Lachnaeus* Schoenherr, 1826

crinitus Schoenherr, 1826 – TMN, TOM, NOV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Larinus* Dejean, 1921

Subgenus *Larinomesius* Reitter, 1924

impressus Gebler, 1829 – NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL [Gültekin (2013) placed *L. variolatus* to synonym of *L. impressus* without studying the type of *L. impressus* based on Petri (1907). *L. impressus* is a large beetle (about 9.0 mm) with a rostrum shorter than the pronotum (Gebler 1929). Five species of the genus *Larinus* (*L. strurnus*, *L. turbinatus*, *L. carlinae*, *L. iaceae* and *L. ruber*) live in the vicinity of Ridder (=Riddersk), East Kazakhstan. Only *L. ruber* is in keeping with the description of *L. impressus*].

=*ruber* Motschulsky, 1845, **syn. nov.**

=*ferrugineus* Capiomont, 1784

[*obtusus* Gyllenhal, 1835 – record of this species from “PRIM” (Ter-Minassian 1967) is wrong].

[*serratulae* Becker, 1864 – record of this species from “Transbaicalia” (Ter-Minassian 1967) is wrong].

Subgenus *Larinus* s. str.

[*latus* (Herbst, 1783) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

pollinis (Laicharting, 1781) – NOV.

=*brevis* Herbst, 1795

[*idoneus* Gyllenhal, 1835 – record of this species from “W. Siberia” (Ter-Minassian 1967) belongs to Kazakhstan].

[*onopordi* (Fabricius, 1787) – record of this species from “W. Siberia” (Ter-Minassian 1967) belongs to Kazakhstan].

=*uniformis* Petri, 1907

[*rudicollis* Petri, 1907 – records of this species from “Siberia” (Ter-Minassian 1967) and “W Siberia” (Fremuth 1982) belong to Kazakhstan].

[*sibiricus* Gyllenhal, 1835– record of this species from “W. Siberia” (Ter-Minassian 1967) belongs to Kazakhstan].

[*ursus* (Fabricius, 1792) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

vulpes (Olivier, 1807) – CHEL, “CHT” (Ter-Minassian 1967).

Subgenus *Phyllonomeus* Gistel, 1856

carlinae (Olivier, 1807) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT.

=*planus* Fabricius, 1792

centaurii (Olivier, 1807) – CHEL.

=*beckeri* Petri, 1907

iaceae (Fabricius, 1775) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL.

griseopilosus Roelofs, 1873 – KHAB, PRIM, KUR.

=*formosus* Petri, 1907

=*kishidai* Kono, 1935

meleagris Petri, 1907 – SAKH, KUR.

[*pruinus* Petri, 1907 – record of this species from “W Siberia” (Ter-Minassian 1967) is wrong].

[*rectinasus* Petri, 1907 – record of this species from “KRN” (Ter-Minassian 1967) is wrong].

sturnus (Schaller, 1783) – TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL.

latissimus Roelofs, 1873 – BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, KUR.

=*subvariolosus* Petri, 1907

scabrirostris Faldermann, 1835 – IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

turbinatus Gyllenhal, 1835 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, IRK.

variolasus Petri, 1907, **stat. res.** – KHAB, AMUR, PRIM.

Genus *Lixus* Fabricius, 1801

Subgenus *Broconius* Desbrochers des Loges, 1904

korotyaevi Ter-Minassian, 1984 – TUV, BUR.

rubicundus Zoubkoff, 1833 – CHEL, NOV, KEM.

Subgenus *Callistolixus* Reitter, 1916

cylindrus (Fabricius, 1781) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, NOV, ALT, RAL.

Subgenus *Compsolixus* Reitter, 1916*albomarginatus* Boheman, 1842 – CHEL, OMS, NOV, ALT.*fairmairei* Faust, 1890 – TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, PRIM.**Subgenus *Dilixellus* Reitter, 1916***bardanae* (Fabricius, 1787) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.*depressipennis* Roelofs, 1873 – PRIM.*fasciculatus* Boheman, 1835 – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.=*maculatus* Roelofs, 1873, **syn. nov.** [*L. maculatus* has no significant differences from *L. fasciculatus* and belongs to this species].*formaneki* Reitter, 1895 – TUV, BUR, CHT, AMUR.*impressiventris* Roelofs, 1873 – “Siberia” (Hong et al. 2000).*obliquus* Faust, 1884 – TUV, BUR.=*emeljanovi* Ter-Minassian, 1972*pulverulentus* (Scopoli 1763) – CHEL.**Subgenus *Epimeces* Billberg, 1820***cardui* Olivier, 1807 – OMS, KEM.*filiiformis* (Fabricius, 1781) – TMN, ALT.**Subgenus *Eulixus* Reitter, 1916***acutipennis* Roelofs, 1873 – AMUR, PRIM.[*coloratus* Petri, 1904 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].*desertorum* Gebler, 1829 – ALT.*divaricatus* Motschulsky, 1861 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.*iris* Olivier, 1807 – TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, YAK.*myagri* Olivier, 1807 – NOV.*pyrrhocnemis* Boheman, 1842 – “Siberia” (Ter-Minassian 1967).[*trichromus* Alonso-Zarazaga, 2016 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].**Subgenus *Lixus* s. str.***paraplecticus* (Linnaeus, 1758) – KHM, TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, ALT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.**Subgenus *Ortholixus* Reitter, 1916***amurensis* Faust, 1887 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.**Subgenus *Phillixus* Petri, 1904***brevipes* Brisout de Barneville, 1866 – TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR.=*irkutensis* Faust, 1895*subtilis* Boheman, 1835 – CHEL, OMS, NOV, ALT, TUV, BUR, AMUR, KHAB.

Genus *Rhinocyllus* Germar, 1817

conicus (Frolich, 1792) – TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL.

Tribe Cleonini Schoenherr, 1826

Genus *Adosomus* Faust, 1904

Subgenus *Adosomus* s. str.

karelini (Fahraeus, 1842) – ALT, RAL, IRK, BUR.

Subgenus *Pseudoadosomus* Arzanov, 2005

granulosus (Mannerheim, 1825) – BUR, CHT, AMUR, PRIM.

melanogrammus (Motschulsky, 1854) – “PRIM” (Ter-Minassian 1988).

Subgenus *Xeradosomus* Arzanov, 2005

grigorievi Suvorov, 1915 – TUV.

[*samsonowii* (Gebler, 1844) – record of this species from “W Siberia” (Ter-Minassian 1988) belongs to East-Kazakhstan Prov.].

Genus *Asproparthenis* Gozis, 1886

carinata (Zubkoff, 1892) – OMS, NOV, ALT, RAL.

=*halophilus* Gebler, 1830

carinicollis (Gyllenhal, 1834) – OMS, NOV, ALT,

foveocollis (Gebler, 1834) – TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, BUR.

[*leucophaea* (Ménétriés, 1849) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

libitinaris (Faust, 1886) – TUV, BUR, CHT. [The records of *A. securo* (Faust, 1890) from Siberia belong to this species].

[*obsoletefasciata* (Ménétriés, 1849) – record of this species from “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017) belongs to Kazakhstan].

punctiventris (Germar, 1823) – NOV, ALT,

salebrosicollis (Fahraeus, 1842) – RAL, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

vexata (Gyllenhal, 1834) – TMN, OMS, NOV, ALT, CHT.

Insertae sedis

atrirostris (Gebler, 1832) – “CHT” (Perrin and Meregalli 2007).

Genus *Atactogaster* Faust, 1904

[*inducens* (Walker, 1859) – record of this species from “PRIM” (Egorov 1976b) is wrong].

=*bisignatus* Roelofs, 1783

Genus *Bothynoderes* Schoenherr, 1823

affinis (Schrank, 1781) – KURG, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT.

declivis (Olivier, 1807) – OMS, NOV, ALT, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Chromonotus* Motschulsky, 1860**Subgenus *Chevrolatius* Arzanov, 2006**

bipunctatus (Zubkoff, 1829) – NOV, ALT, TUV, BUR, CHT.

=*humeralis* Zubkoff, 1829

[*hirsutululus* (Faust, 1883) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

[*pilosellus* (Fåhraeus, 1842) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

[*vittatus* (Zoubkoff, 1829) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Genus *Cleonis* Dejean, 1821

japonica japonica (Faust, 1904) – BUR, CHT, AMUR, PRIM.

japonica hasujizo Kôno, 1929 – KUR.

neglecta Ter-Minassian et Egorov, 1981 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

pigra (Scopoli, 1763) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK.

Genus *Conioleonus* Motschulsky, 1860**Subgenus *Angarocleonus* Arzanov, 2006**

astragali Ter-Minassian et Korotyaev, 1977 – RAL, CHUK, KAM, MAG.

cinerascens (Hochhut, 1851) – RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, CHUK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

cineritius (Gyllenhal, 1834) – BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

elisabetae Ter-Minassian et Korotyaev, 1977 – BUR, CHT, AMUR.

ferrugineus (Fåhraeus, 1842) – OMS, TOM, NOV, KHA, RAL, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

[*vittiger* Fåhraeus, 1842 – record of this species from “Transbaicalia” (Csiki 1934a) is wrong].

zherichini Ter-Minassian et Korotyaev, 1977 – YAN, KAM, CHUK, KAM, MAG.

Subgenus *Augustecleonus* Arzanov, 2006

[*hollbergi* (Fåhraeus, 1842) – record of this species from “Siberia” (Ter-Minassian 1988) is wrong].

turbatus (Fåhraeus, 1842) – YAN.

Subgenus *Coliocleonus* s. str.

schoenherri (Gebler, 1829) – KEM, ALT, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

vinokurovi Ter-Minassian et Korotyaev, 1977 – YAK, MAG, AMUR.

Subgenus *Plagiographus* Chevrolat, 1869

[*nigrosuturatus* (Goeze, 1777) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Genus *Conorhynchus* Motschulsky, 1860

Subgenus *Conorhynchus* s. str.

conirostris (Gebler, 1829) – OMS, ALT, TUV, BUR, CHT.

[*kindermanni* Faust, 1904 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

[*lacerta* Chevrolat, 1873 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

[*nigrivittis* (Pallas, 1781) – “W Siberia” (Ter-Minassian 1988), “CHT” (Zherichin and Egorov 1991)].

[*schrenkii* (Gebler, 1844) – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Genus *Cyphocleonus* Motschulsky, 1860

[*achates* (Fåhræus, 1842) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

altaicus (Gebler, 1829) – TMN, OMS, NOV, ALT.

= *adumbratus* Gebler, 1833, **syn. res.**

dealbatus (Gmelin, 1790) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, NOV, ALT.

immemoratus Ter-Minassian, 1962 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

trisolcatus (Herbst, 1795) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, KHA.

Genus *Epexochus* Reitter, 1913

[*lehmanni* (Ménétriés, 1849) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Genus *Eumecops* Hochhut, 1851

fasciculifer Reitter, 1895 – BUR, CHT, AMUR.

tuberculatus (Gebler, 1829) – ALT.

Insertae sedis

spicatus Chevrolat, 1873 – “Siberia” (Ter-Minassian 1988).

Genus *Leucomigus* Motschulsky, 1860

[*candidatus candidatus* (Pallas, 1771) – record of this species from “Sibirien” (Csiki, 1934a) is wrong].

Genus *Maximus* Alonso-Zarazaga et Lyal, 2009

[*obnoxius* (Fåhræus, 1842) – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

[*strabus* (Gyllenhal, 1834) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

[*verrucosus* (Gebler, 1829) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Genus *Microcleonus* Faust, 1904

panderi (Fischer de Waldheim, 1835) – IRK, BUR, CHT.

= *sedakovi* Boheman, 1842

Genus *Pachycerus* Schoenherr, 1823*costatulus* Faust, 1890 – BUR.*segnis* (Germar, 1823) – NOV, ALT.**Genus *Pleurocleonus* Motschulsky, 1860***bicarinatus* (Gebler, 1829) – [It is probably a synonym of *P. sollicitus*, only one specimen from Khabarovskii Krai is characterized by a finely punctate pronotum without rugosity].*quadrivittatus* (Zoubkoff, 1829) – NOV, ALT, RAL, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT.*sollicitus* (Gyllenhal, 1834) – NOV, ALT, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.**Genus *Pseudocleonus* Chevrolat, 1873****Subgenus *Asiacleonus* Arzanov, 2005***dauricus* (Gebler, 1829) – TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, BUR, CHT, AMUR.**Subgenus *Pseudocleonus* s. str.***cinereus* (Schrank, 1781) – KURG, RAL, IRK.**Genus *Rhabdorrhynchus* Motschulsky, 1860***seriegranosus* Chevrolat, 1873 – ALT, RAL.**Genus *Scaphomorphus* Motschulsky, 1860***foveolaticollis* (Ter-Minassian, 1989) – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].*pallasi* Faust, 1890 – TUV, BUR, CHT.*vibex* (Pallas, 1781) – RAL, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR.**Genus *Stephanocleonus* Motschulsky, 1860****Subgenus *Eremocleonus* Ter-Minassian, 1974***chankanus* Suvorov, 1915 – PRIM.*costatus* (Gebler, 1832) – TUV, BUR, CHT, AMUR.=*bicostatus* Gebler, 1833*[fascicularis* (Gebler, 1833) – record of this species from “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017) belongs to Kazakhstan].*ferox* Faust, 1883 – BUR, CHT.*gobianus* Suvorov, 1912 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).= *analis* Voss, 1967*hirtipes* Faust, 1904 – BUR, CHT.*superciliosus* (Gebler, 1832) – BUR, CHT, AMUR.=*lobatus* Chevrolat, 1873

Subgenus *Sanzia* Alonso-Zarazaga et Lyal, 1999

[*tetragrammus* (Pallas, 1781) – record of this species from “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017) belongs to Kazakhstan].

Subgenus *Stephanocleonus* s. str.

amurensis Ter-Minassian, 1976 – BUR, CHT, AMUR.

anceps Chevrolat, 1873 – TUV, “Transbaicalia” (Ter-Minassian 1988).

bifasciatus Ter-Minassian, 1979 – TUV.

bonus Ter-Minassian, 1979 – TUV.

coelebs Faust, 1883 – “W Siberia” (Ter-Minassian 1979).

confessus Faust, 1904 – “BUR, CHT” (Ter-Minassian 1979).

deportatus Chevrolat, 1873 – TUV, BUR, PRIM.

dubius Faust, 1904 – TUV, BUR, CHT.

edithae Reitter, 1895 – “BUR” (Ter-Minassian 1979).

eduardi Ter-Minassian et Korotyayev, 1978 – RAL, TUV, BUR.

eruditus Faust, 1890 – KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, YAK.

favens Faust, 1884 – RAL, TUV, BUR.

fenestratus (Pallas, 1781) – BUR, CHT.

fossulatus (Fischer von Waldheim, 1823) – RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB.

foveifrons Chevrolat, 1873 – IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK.

grigorievi Suvorov, 1915 – RAL, TUV.

hammarstroemi Faust, 1890 – TUV.

[*henningi* (Fahraeus, 1842) – record of this species from “Siberia” (Ter-Minassian 1979) belongs to East-Kazakhstan Prov.].

hexagrammus (Fahraeus, 1842) – BUR.

illex Faust, 1904 – RAL.

impressicollis (Fahraeus, 1842) – TUV, BUR, CHT.

incertus Ter-Minassian, 1972 – RAL, TUV.

ingratus Ter-Minassian, 1979 – TUV.

isochromus Suvorov, 1912 – RAL.

jucundus Faust, 1890 – TUV.

kobdoanus (Suvorov, 1915) – TUV.

korinii (Fahraeus, 1842) – “TUV” (Ter-Minassian 1979).

leucopterus (Fischer von Waldheim, 1823) – NOV, KEM, ALT, KHA, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR [The types of *S. jakovlevi* and *S. jennisseicus* are studied, and they belong to the *S. leucopterus* distributed in Kazakhstan and Siberia].

=*jakovlevi* Faust, 1893, **syn. nov.**

=*jennisseicus* Ter-Minassian, 1978, **syn. nov.**

ljudmilae Ter-Minassian et Korotyayev, 1978 – RAL, TUV.

lukjanovitshi Ter-Minassian, 1975 – TUV.

mannerheimi Chevrolat, 1873 – RAL, TUV, BUR, CHT.

- marginatus* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1823) – ALT, CHT.
medvedevi Ter-Minassian, 1984 – CHT.
nassiformis (Goeze, 1777) – TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT.
 =*flaviceps* Pallas, 1781
novus Ter-Minassian, 1978 – TUV.
nubilis (Fahraeus, 1842) – IRK, BUR.
opporthunus Faust, 1890 – TUV.
paradoxus paradoxus (Fahraeus, 1842) – RAL, TUV, BUR, CHT.
pellax Ter-Minassian, 1979 – TUV.
prasolovi Ter-Minassian, 1990 – RAL.
roddi Suvorov, 1912 – RAL, TUV.
sahlbergi Faust, 1890 – TUV.
setinasus Faust, 1890 – KHA, TUV.
 [*simulans* Faust, 1883 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].
suffusus Faust, 1904 – “Transbaicalia” (Ter-Minassian 1984).
tardus Faust, 1904 – TUV.
tricarinatus (Fischer von Waldheim, 1823) – RAL, IRK, BUR, CHT.
trifasciatus Faust, 1891 – KHA, TUV, BUR, CHT.
tschuicus Suvorov, 1912 – RAL, TUV.
tuvensis Ter-Minassian, 1978 – TUV.
verestschagini Suvorov, 1912 – RAL.
versutus Faust, 1904 – BUR, CHT.
 Insertae sedis
canaliculatus (Gebler, 1830) – “RAL” (Heyden 1880-1881).
depressus (Gebler, 1829) – “RAL” (Perrin and Meregalli 2007).
renardii (Gebler, 1848) – “RAL” (Perrin and Meregalli 2007).

Subgenus *Taenioleonus* Ter-Minassian, 1974

- albofasciatus* Ter-Minassian, 1972 – TUV, BUR.
altaicus Ter-Minassian et Korotyayev, 1978 – RAL.
ehnbergi Faust, 1890 – TUV.
excisus Reitter, 1895 – BUR, CHT.
giganteus Ter-Minassian, 1970 – TUV.
jacobsoni Faust, 1904 – TUV.
korotjaevi Ter-Minassian, 1979 – RAL, TUV, BUR.
luctuosus Faust, 1895 – KHA, TUV.
sibiricus Ter-Minassian, 1970 – KHA.
suvorovi Legalov, 1999 – RAL.
 =*plumbeus* Suvorov, 1912
thoracicus (Fischer von Waldheim, 1835) – IRK, BUR, CHT.
waldheimi Faust, 1904 – IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR.

Genus *Xanthochelus* Chevrolat, 1873

nomas (Pallas, 1771) – TOM, “Siberia” (Ter-Minassian 1988).

Subfamily Dryophthorinae Schoenherr, 1825

Tribe Orthognathini Lacordaire, 1866

Genus *Sipalinus* Marshall, 1943

gigas gigas (Fabricius, 1775) – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

Tribe Dryophthorini Schoenherr, 1825

Genus *Dryophthorus* Germar, 1823

corticalis (Paykull, 1792) – PRIM.

konishii Morimoto, 1985 – PRIM, KUR.

sculpturatus (Wollaston, 1873) – “KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR” (Egorov and Zherichin 1996).

Tribe Litosomini Lacordaire, 1866

Subtribe Sitophila Csiki, 1936

Genus *Sitophilus* Schoenherr, 1838

granarius (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, PRIM.

oryzae (Linnaeus, 1763) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, PRIM.

Tribe Sphenophorini Lacordaire, 1866

Subtribe Sphenophorina Lacordaire, 1866

Genus *Sphenophorus* Schoenherr, 1838

abbreviatus (Fabricius, 1787) – OMS, NOV, ALT.

kuznetzovi (Egorov, 1979) – PRIM.

piceus (Pallas, 1776) – “ALT” (Heyden 1880-1881).

striatopunctatus (Goeze, 1777) – RAL.

Subfamily Cossoninae Schoenherr, 1825

Tribe Rhyncolini Gistel, 1856

Subtribe Stenoscelidina Wollaston, 1877

Genus *Hexarthrum* Wollaston, 1860

chinense Folwaczny, 1968 – PRIM.

Genus *Miorrhinus* Marshall, 1936

nanus Zherichin, 1991 – PRIM.

pilirostris Zherichin, 1991 – KUR.

Genus *Stenoscelis* Wollaston, 1861**Subgenus *Stenoscelis* s. str.***acutipennis* Zherichin, 1991 – KUR.*cryptomeriae* Konishi, 1962 – PRIM.**Genus *Trichacorynus* Blatchley, 1916***subtilis* (Korotyaev, 1976) – KAM.**Subtribe *Phloeophagina* Voss, 1955****Genus *Phloeophagus* Schoenherr, 1838***orientalis* Osella, 1974 – PRIM, KUR.*turbatus* Boheman, 1845 – TMN, TOM, NOV, ALT, RAL, BUR, AMUR.[*thomsoni* Grill, 1898– “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].**Subtribe *Rhyncolina* Gistel, 1856****Genus *Rhyncolus* Germar, 1817****Subgenus *Axenomimetes* Voss, 1955***heydeni* Faust, 1892 – “Western Siberia (Altai)” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).**Subgenus *Rhyncolus* s. str.***ater ater* (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, IRK, BUR, YAK.*ater curvistriatus* Zherichin, 1991 – SAKH, KUR.*elongatus* (Gyllenhal, 1827) – KEM, RAL.*macrops* Buchanan, 1946 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.*sculpturatus* Waltl, 1839 – BUR, Khab, PRIM, KUR.**Genus *Xenomimetes* Wollaston, 1873***alni* Konishi, 1955 – SAKH, KUR.*destructor* Wollaston, 1873 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.*maritimus* Zherichin, 1991 – SAKH.*rarus* Zherichin, 1991 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.**Tribe *Cossonini* Schoenherr, 1826****Genus *Cossonus* Clairville, 1798****Subgenus *Caenocossonus* Voss, 1955***cylindricus* C. Sahlberg, 1835 – ALT, RAL, KAM, AMUR, Khab, PRIM.*gibbistrotris* Roelofs, 1875 – KUR.*rotundicollis* Faust, 1882 – AMUR, Khab, PRIM, SAKH.= *piniphilus* Folwaczny, 1968*tibialis* Folwaczny, 1964 – PRIM, KUR.

Subgenus *Cossonus* s. str.

linearis (Fabricius, 1775) – ALT.

Genus *Orthotemnus* Wollaston, 1873

ulmi Zherichin, 1991 – PRIM, SAKH.

Genus *Oxydema* Wollaston, 1873

aksentjevi Zherichin, 1991 – KUR.

Genus *Phloeophagosoma* Wollaston, 1873

Subgenus *Phloeophagosoma* s. str.

exile Zherichin, 1991 – KUR.

rufirostre Zherichin, 1991 – KUR.

Tribe Himatinini Konishi, 1962

Genus *Ochronanus* Pascoe, 1885

pallidus Marshall, 1958 – KUR.

Genus *Himatium* Wollaston, 1873

Subgenus *Himatium* s. str.

korotyaevi Zherichin, 1991 – KUR.

piceae (Konishi, 1962) – SAKH.

Subfamily Conoderinae Schoenherr, 1833

Supertribe Bariditae Schoenherr, 1836

Tribe Apostasimerini Schoenherr, 1844

Subtribe Diorymerina Jekel, 1865

=Zygobaridina Pierce, 1907

=Limnobarini Casey, 1922

Genus *Centrinopsis* Roelofs, 1875

nitens Roelofs, 1875 – “SAKH” (Egorov et al. 1996).

Genus *Limnobaris* Bedel, 1885

albosparsa Reitter, 1910 – KHAB, PRIM.

dolorosa (Goeze, 1777) – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, KUR.

=*jucunda* Reitter, 1910

japonica Yoshihara et Morimoto, 1994 – “SAKH” (Egorov et al. 1996).

t-album (Linnaeus, 1758) – CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN, KHA.

= *atriplicis* Fabricius, 1792

Tribe Baridini Schoenherr, 1836**Subtribe Baridina Schoenherr, 1836****Genus *Anthinobaris* Morimoto et Yoshihara, 1996**

dispilota dispilota (Solsky, 1870) – BUR, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Aulacobaris* Desbrochers des Loges, 1892

janthina (Boheman, 1836) – CHEL, NOV, KEM, ALT.

lepidii (Germar, 1823) – NOV, ALT.

kaszabi Korotyaev, 1995 – IRK.

violaceomicans violaceomicans (F. Solari, 1904) – NOV.

Genus *Baris* Germar, 1817

analis analis (Olivier, 1791) – AMUR.

artemisiae (Herbst, 1794) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

auliensis Reitter, 1901 – NOV, RAL, KHA.

charbinensis Zaslavskij, 1956 – KHAB.

kiritshenkoi Zaslavskij, 1956 – RAL, TUV.

nesapia Faust, 1887 – TMN, NOV, ALT, CHT.

sulcata (Boheman, 1836) – ALT.

Genus *Cosmobaris* Casey, 1920

scolopacea (Germar, 1823) – OMS, NOV, ALT, KHA, PRIM.

=*borkhsenii* Zaslavskij, 1956

Genus *Eremobaris* Zaslavskij, 1956

[*picturata* (Ménétriés, 1849) – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Genus *Labiaticola* Alomzo-Zarazaga et Lyal, 1999

sibiricus (Faust, 1890) – CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, BUR, CHT, AMUR.

Genus *Neobaris* Reitter, 1895

logunovi Legalov, 1999 – TUV.

Genus *Ulobaris* Reitter, 1895

kuchenbeisseri (Hartmann, 1899) – BUR, CHT, AMUR, PRIM.

=*ussuriensis* Zaslavskij, 1956

=*chinganensis* Zaslavskij, 1956

=*pseudospitzyi* Zaslavskij, 1956

Tribe Madarini Jekel, 1865

Subtribe Neosharpiina Hoffmann, 1956

Genus *Athesapeuta* Faust, 1894

gracilis (Voss, 1958) – PRIM.

Genus *Dendrobaris* Egorov, 1976

kurentzovi (Egorov, 1976) – PRIM.

tatjanae (Egorov, 1976) – NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Moreobaris* Morimoto et Yoshihara, 1996

repandirostris (Zaslavskij, 1956) – PRIM.

Genus *Nespilobaris* Morimoto et Yoshihara, 1996

accidirostris (Zaslavskii, 1956) – KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Pellobaris* Morimoto et Yoshihara, 1996

melancholica (Roelofs, 1875) – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Pharcidobaris* Morimoto et Yoshihara, 1996

pilosa (Roelofs, 1875) – RAL, KHA, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

=*suvorovi* Reitter, 1910

=*piliventris* Zaslavskij, 1956

Genus *Psilarthroides* Morimoto et Miyakawa, 1985

czerskyi Zaslavskij, 1956 – KHAB, PRIM.

=*laferi* Egorov, 1976

Supertribe Conoderitae Schoenherr, 1833

Tribe Coryssomerini Thomson, 1859

Genus *Coryssomerus* Schoenherr, 1825

capucinus (Beck, 1817) – TMN.

Genus *Euryommatus* Roger, 1857

mariae Roger, 1857 – NOV, RAL, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

odiosus (Faust, 1882) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

tokioensis Nakane, 1963 – KUR.

triangulus Zumpt, 1937 – KUR.

Genus *Metialma* Pascoe, 1871**Subgenus *Metialma* s. str.**

signifera Pascoe, 1871 – KHAB, PRIM.

Tribe Mecopini Lacordaire, 1866**Genus *Mecopomorphus* Hustache, 1920**

amurensis (Heyden, 1884) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
=*griseus* Hustache, 1920

Genus *Phylaitis* Pascoe, 1871

maculiventris Voss, 1958 – SAKH.

Tribe Menemachini Lacordaire, 1865**Genus *Telephae* Pascoe, 1870**

konoï Morimoto, 1960 – KUR.

Supertribe Ceutorhynchitae Gistel, 1848**Tribe Amalini Wagner, 1936****Genus *Amalus* Schoenherr, 1825**

scortillum (Herbst, 1795) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, TUV, IRK, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Tribe Ceutorhynchini Gistel, 1848**Genus *Amalorrhynchus* Reitter, 1913**

lukjanovitshi Korotyaev, 1980 – NOV, YAK.
melanarius (Stephens, 1831) – TMN, NOV, RAL, PRIM.

Genus *Brevicoeliodes* Korotyaev, 1997

galloisi (Hustache, 1916) – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov and Basarukina 1981).

Genus *Calosirus* C. G. Thomson, 1859

apicalis (Gyllenhal 1827) – NOV, KEM.

Genus *Cardipennis* Korotyaev, 1980

rubripes (Hustache, 1916) – CHEL, IRK, BUR, CHT, PRIM.
shaowuensis (Voss, 1958) – PRIM.
sulcithorax (Hustache, 1916) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Ceutorhynchus* Germar, 1823

- adustus* Korotyaev, 1980 – CHT.
affinis Ch. Brisout de Barneville, 1883 – KHA, KRN.
albosuturalis (Roelofs, 1875) – AMUR, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
alexanderi Korotyaev, 2017 – PRIM.
arator Gyllenhal, 1837 – TOM, RAL, KRN, IRK.
arborator Korotyaev, 1998 – KRN, TUV, IRK.
argenteomontanus Korotyaev, 1980 – TUV.
asiaticus Korotyaev, 1997 – KUR.
assimilis (Paykull, 1792) – KRN.
=*pleurostigma* Marsham, 1802
barbareae Sufferian, 1847 – TOM, NOV.
barkalovi Korotyaev, 1977 – YAN, RAL, KRN, TUV, BUR, CHUK.
belovi Korotyaev, 1995 – KHAB.
biseriatus Faust, 1885 – TMN.
buniadis Penecke, 1928 – BUR.
canaliculatus C. Brisout de Barneville, 1869 – TMN, NOV.
chalybaeus Germar, 1823 – CHEL, NOV, IRK.
cochleariae (Gyllenhal, 1813) – RAL, KRN, IRK.
contractus (Marsham, 1802) – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, IRK.
=*pallipes* Crotch, 1866
dauricus Korotyaev, 1997 – CHT, AMUR, PRIM.
demetrii Korotyaev, 1995 – KHAB.
erysimi (Fabricius, 1787) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN, YAK, PRIM.
fabrilis Faust, 1887 – CHEL, KURG, NOV, ALT, PRIM.
filiae Dalla Torre, 1922 – PRIM.
gallorhenanus F. Solari, 1949 – TMN, CHEL, NOV, KEM, ALT, IRK.
granulicollis Thomson, 1865 – KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, ALT.
hampei (Ch. Brisout de Barneville, 1869) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK.
ignitus Germar, 1823 – KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN.
inaffectatus Gyllenhal, 1837 – “Siberia” (Winkler 1930-1932).
khnzoriani Korotyaev, 1980 – IRK.
kipchak Korotyaev, 1996 – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN.
klementzorum Korotyaev, 1980 – IRK, YAK.
kolymensis Korotyaev, 1980 – MAG.
linicola Korotyaev, 1980 – KRN, TUV, CHT, YAK.
marmoratus Korotyaev, 1980 – YAK.
matisi Korotyaev, 1995 – KRN, BUR, MAG.
nitidulus Faust, 1887 – PRIM.
niyazii Hoffmann, 1957 – OMS.
obstrictus (Marsham, 1802) – “South of the Russian Far East” (Hong et al. 2000).
pectoralis Weise, 1895 – “Siberia” (Dieckmann 1972).

- pervicax* Weise, 1883 – IRK.
piceolatus (Ch. Brisout de Barneville, 1883) – NOV, IRK, YAK.
plumbeus Ch. Brisot, 1869 – NOV.
potanini Korotyaev, 1980 – YAK.
problematicus Korotyaev, 1980 – SAKH, KUR
pseudarator Korotyaev, 1989 – RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK.
pulvinatus Gyllenhal, 1837 – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK.
puncticollis Boheman, 1845 – TMN, NOV, ALT.
 [pyrrhorhynchus (Marshall, 1802) – record of this species from “Siberia” (Winkler 1930-1932) is wrong].
querceti (Gyllenhal, 1813) – TMN, TOM, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB.
rapae Gyllenhal, 1837 – KHM, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, YAK, MAG, KAM, PRIM.
rhenanus (Schultze, 1895) – CHEL, TOM, NOV, ALT, CHT.
robustus Korotyaev, 1980 – RAL, IRK, AMUR, PRIM.
rusticus Gyllenhal, 1837 – RAL.
scapularis Gyllenhal, 1837 – TMN, TOM, NOV, IRK, CHT, MAG, PRIM.
seniculus Ch. Brisout de Barneville, 1883 – RAL, TUV, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, PRIM.
simulans Korotyaev, 1980 – TUV, CHT.
sinicus (Voss, 1958) – KUR.
sisymbrii (Dieckmann, 1966) – NOV, KEM, IRK.
sophiae Gyllenhal, 1837 – TOM, NOV, IRK.
subcoeruleipennis Voss, 1958 – PRIM.
 =*philippovi* Korotyaev, 1980
sulcicollis (Paykull, 1800) – NOV.
syrites Germar, 1823 – CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, IRK.
tesquorum Korotyaev, 1980 – TUV.
testatus Faust, 1890 – NOV, RAL, TUV, IRK.
tolli Korotyaev, 1980 – YAK.
turbatus Schultze, 1903 – ALT.
typhae (Herbst, 1795) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN, TUV, IRK.
 =*floralis* Paykull, 1792
unguicularis Thomson, 1871 – TUV, PRIM, KUR.
ussuricus Korotyaev, 1997 – KHAB, PRIM.
viridanus Gyllenhal, 1837 – NOV, ALT, RAL, KHA, KRN, TUV, YAK.
zherichini Korotyaev, 2017 – PRIM.

Genus *Coeliodes* Schoenherr, 1837

- babai* Voss et Chujo, 1960 – AMUR, PRIM.
 =*zinovjevi* Korotyaev, 1997

kasparyani Korotyaev, 1997 – KHAB, PRIM.
nakanoensis Hustache, 1916 – AMUR, PRIM.

Genus *Coeliodinus* Dieckmann, 1972

etorofuensis (Kono, 1935) – SAKH, KUR.
=*insularis* Korotyaev, 1997
nigritarsis (Hartmann, 1895) – YAN, TOM, KEM, IRK, BUR, CHT, MAG, KAM, KHAB, PRIM, KUR.
rubicundus (Herbst, 1795) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, TOM, KEM, RAL.
parcesquamosus (Hustache, 1916) – PRIM.
sibiricus (Reitter, 1916) – IRK, BUR, MAG, KHAB, PRIM.
subrubicundus (Reitter, 1916) – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

Genus *Datonychus* Wagner, 1944

angulosus (Boheman, 1845) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM.
arquata (Herbst, 1795) – TMN, NOV, ALT, AMUR, PRIM.

Genus *Glocianus* Reitter, 1916

cupidus (Faust, 1895) – IRK.
distinctus (Ch. Brisout de Barneville, 1870) – TMN, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT.
fennicus (Faust, 1895) – TMN, TUV, IRK, CHT, YAK, PRIM.
moelleri (Thomson, 1868) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN.
punctiger (C.R. Sahlberg, 1835) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN, IRK, CHT, YAK, AMUR, SAKH.

Genus *Hadroplontus* Thomson, 1859

ancora (Roelofs, 1875) – AMUR, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
litura (Fabricius, 1775) – TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN.

Genus *Hemioxyonyx* Korotyaev, 1982

[*acutangulus* (Schultze, 1903) – record of this species from “Siberia” (Winkler 1930-1932) is wrong].

Genus *Microplontus* Wagner, 1944

amurensis Korotyaev, 2004 – KHAB.
campestris (Gyllenhal, 1837) – TMN, NOV, KEM,
egorovi (Korotyaev, 1980) – PRIM.
millefolii (Schultze, 1897) – TMN, NOV, KEM, RAL.
rugulosus (Herbst, 1795) – NOV, KEM.
=*figuratus* Gyllenhal, 1837
triangulum (Boheman, 1845) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN, IRK, CHT, PRIM.

Genus *Mogulones* Reitter, 1916

asperifoliarum (Gyllenhal, 1813) – TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN.

austriacus (Ch. Brisout de Barneville, 1869) – CHEL, KURG, OMS, NOV, ALT.

crucifer (Pallas, 1771) – KURG, NOV, KEM, KRN.

cynoglossi (Frauenfeld, 1866) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

dimidiatus (Fruvaldsky, 1865) – OMS, NOV.

larvatus (Schultze, 1897) – TOM, NOV, KEM, KRN, IRK.

pallidicornis (Gougelet et H. Brisout de Barneville, 1860) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK.

tresignatus (Gyllenhal, 1837) – NOV.

Genus *Nedyus* Schoenherr, 1825

quadrimaculatus (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, IRK, CHT, PRIM, SAKH.

Genus *Oprohinus* Reitter, 1916

jakovlevi (Schultze, 1902) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, KRN.

sibiricus (Faust, 1895) – IRK.

Genus *Parethelcus* Wagner, 1943

pollinarius (Forster, 1771) – TMN.

Genus *Poophagus* Schoenherr, 1837

hopffgarteni Tournier, 1873 – KHM, NOV, KRN.

robustus Faust, 1882 – NOV.

sisymbrii (Fabricius, 1777) – KHM, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, YAK.

Genus *Prisistus* Reitter, 1916

caucasicus bohemani (Colonnelli, 1985) – NOV, TUV, CHT, PRIM.

olgae (Korotyaev, 1988) – CHUK.

subovatus (Korotyaev, 1980) – PRIM.

vadimi Korotyaev, 1998 – TUV.

zinovjevi (Krotyaev, 1980) – AMUR.

Genus *Ranunculiphilus* Dieckmann, 1969**Subgenus *Ranunculiphilus* Dieckmann, 1969**

inclemens (Faust, 1888) – TOM, KEM, RAL, KRN, IRK, MAG, PRIM.

pseudinclemens (Dieckmann, 1970) – KRN.

Genus *Sinocolus* Korotyaev, 1996

charbinensis (Stoecklein, 1954) – CHT, AMUR, PRIM.

Genus *Sirocalodes* Voss, 1958

kasparyani Korotyaev, 1980 – PRIM.

marshakovi Korotyaev, 1980 – NOV, KEM, ALT, IRK, MAG.

notatus (Brisout de Barneville, 1883) – KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR.

=*czekanovskiyi* Korotyaev, 1980

quericola (Paykull, 1792) – TMN, KEM, IRK, PRIM.

urbinus (Hustache, 1916) – SAKH.

Genus *Stenocarus* Thomson, 1859

ruficornis (Stephens, 1831) – NOV.

Genus *Svetlaniolus* Korotyaev, 1997

jurganovae (Korotyaev, 1980) – KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, KRN.

Genus *Thamiocolus* Thomson, 1859

fausti (Ch. Brisout de Barneville, 1883) – IRK, KHAN, PRIM.

gobicola Korotyaev, 1980 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

kerzhneri Korotyaev, 1980 – TUV, BUR, CHT.

kraatzi (Ch. Brisout de Barneville, 1869) – TMN, NOV, AMUR, KHAB.

nubeculosus (Gyllenhal, 1837) – TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, CHT, YAK, PRIM.

sahlbergi (C.R. Sahlberg, 1845) – CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK.

[*signatus* (Gyllenhal, 1837) – record of this species from “Siberia” (Dieckmann 1972) is wrong].

[*uniformis* (Gyllenhal, 1837) – record of this species from “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017) is wrong].

viduatus (Gyllenhal, 1813) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM.

virgatus (Gyllenhal, 1837) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, IRK, BUR, CHT, PRIM.

Genus *Trichosirocalus* Colonnelli, 1979

barnevillei (Grenier, 1866) – TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN, IRK.

horridus (Panzer, 1801) – TMN, ALT, IRK.

troglogytes (Fabricius, 1787) – TMN.

Genus *Wagnerinus* Korotyaev, 1980

carinulatus (Faust, 1887) – PRIM.

shikotanus Korotyaev, 1981 – KUR.

Genus *Zacladus* Reitter, 1913

Subgenus *Amurocladus* Korotyaev, 1997

asperulus (Faust, 1893) – BUR, CHT, PRIM.

Subgenus *Angarocladus* Korotyaev, 1997

radula (Hochhut, 1851) – TOM, KEM, RAL, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, PRIM.

Subgenus *Gobicladus* Korotyaev, 1997

thomsoni (Schultze, 1901) – RAL, TUV, IRK, BYR, CHT.

Subgenus *Zacladus* s. str.

geranii (Paykull, 1800) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, CHT, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, KUR.

Insertae sedis

stierlini Schultze, 1902 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

Tribe Scleropterini Schultze, 1902**Genus *Homorosoma* Frivaldsky, 1894**

asperum (Roelofs, 1875) – AMUR, PRIM.

aterrimum (Hustache, 1916) – PRIM.

validirostre (Gyllenhal, 1837) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

Genus *Rhinoncomimus* Wagner, 1940**Subgenus *Homorosomulus* Korotyaev, 2006**

latipes Korotyaev, 1997 – PRIM.

Genus *Rutidosoma* Stephens, 1831**Subgenus *Rutidosoma* s. str.**

graminosum (Gistel, 1857) – TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, IRK, CHT, AMUR, PRIM.

=*globulus* Herbst, 1795

Genus *Scleropteroides* Colonnelli, 1979

[*hypocrita* (Hustache, 1916) – record of this species from “PRIM” (Egorov 1979a) is wrong].

Genus *Scleropterus* Schoenherr, 1825

rubi Korotyaev, 1980 – PRIM, SAKH.

verecundus Faust, 1890 – KHM, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, KRN, IRK.

Insertae sedis

klausnitzeri Bajtenov, 1983 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

Genus *Tapinotus* Schoenherr, 1826

sellatus (Fabricius, 1794) – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Tribe Cnemogonini Colonnelli, 1979

Genus *Auleutes* Dietz, 1896

epilobii (Paykull, 1800) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, CHT, YAK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

Genus *Phytobiomorphus* Wagner, 1937

variegatus (Hustache, 1920) – PRIM.

Genus *Sinauleutes* Korotyaev, 1996

bigibbosus (Hustache, 1916) – KUR.

Tribe Mononychini LeConte, 1876

Genus *Mononychus* Germar, 1823

ireos (Pallas, 1773) – NOV, ALT.

punctumalbum (Herbst, 1784) – “Siberia” (Winkler 1930-1932).

vittatus Faldermann, 1835 – KEM, KHA, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Tribe Phytobiini Gistel, 1848

Genus *Eubrychius* Thomson, 1859

velutus (Beck, 1817) – KHA, RAL, BUR, CHT, KAM, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Marmaropus* Schoenherr, 1837

besseri Gyllenhal, 1837 – CHEL, NOV, ALT.

Genus *Neophytobius* Wagner, 1936

egorovi (Korotyaev, 1980) – PRIM

granatus (Gyllenhal, 1835) – KHM, TMN, TOM.

hartmanni (Schultze, 1901) – RAL, KRN, BUR, CHT, PRIM.

muricatus (C. Brisout de Barneville, 1867) – TMN.

quadrinodosus (Gyllenhal, 1813) – KHM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN, IRK.

wuorentausi (Korotyaev, 1990) – KAM.

Genus *Pelenomus* Thomson, 1859

canaliculatus (Fahraeus, 1843) – TMN, NOV, KEM, BUR, YAK.

commari (Panzer, 1795) – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV.

quadricorniger (Colonnelli, 1986) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, IRK, PRIM.

quadrituberculatus (Fabricius, 1787) – KHM, TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, RAL, IRK, CHT, YAK, MAG, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

roelofsi (Hustache, 1916) – “Eastern Siberia” (Colonnelli 2004).

sachalinensis (Korotyaev, 1980) – SAKH.

velaris (Gyllenhal, 1827) – TMN, TOM, NOV, RAL, TUV, IRK, CHT, YAK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

waltoni (Boheman, 1843) – TMN, OMS, TOM, RAL, YAK, PRIM, KUR.

Genus *Phytobius* Schoenherr, 1833

friebi (Wagner, 1939) – CHT, AMUR, PRIM.

japonicus Roelofs, 1875 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

leucogaster (Marsham, 1802) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, NOV, RAL, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Rhinoncus* Schoenherr, 1825

albicinctus Gyllenhal, 1837 – KHM, TMN, TOM, IRK, CHT.

autumnalis Korotyaev 1980 – BUR, CHT.

bosnicus Schultze, 1900 – TOM, NOV, ALT, IRK, CHT, YAK, AMUR, PRIM.

bruchoides (Herbst, 1784) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

cribricollis Hustache, 1916 – SAKH, KUR.

inconspectus (Herbst, 1795) – KHM, TMN, KURG, TOM, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KHA.

jakovlevi Faust, 1893 – IRK, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, KUR.

leucostigma (Marsham, 1802) – TOM, NOV, ALT, BUR, CHT, PRIM, KUR.

nigrotibialis Wagner, 1939 – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

pericarpus (Linnaeus, 1758) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, IRK, KHAB, PRIM.

perpendicularis (Reich, 1797) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, CHT, YAK.

sibiricus Faust, 1893 – KEM, IRK, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

sulcicollis Boheman, 1845 – IRK, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Tribe Mecysmoderini Wagner, 1938

Genus *Coelioderes* Korotyaev, 2004

kerzhneri (Korotyaev, 1994) – KUR.

Supertribe Oorbitae Thomson, 1859

Genus *Orobitis* Germar, 1817

cyanea (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, IRK, CHT, YAK, AMUR, PRIM, KUR.

Subfamily Curculioninae Latreille, 1802

Tribe Ellescini C. G. Thomson, 1859

Subtribe Ellescina C. G. Thomson, 1859

= Anoplini Bedel, 1884

Genus *Anoplus* Germar, 1820

plantaris (Naezen, 1836) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, BUR, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Ellescus* Dejean, 1821

Subgenus *Ellescus* s. str.

bipunctatus (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

scanicus (Paykull, 1792) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, IRK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Subgenus *Anisarctus* Desbrochers des Loges, 1907

infirmus (Herbst, 1795) – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM.

languidus Faust, 1882 – CHT, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

=*schoenherri* Faust, 1887

Genus *Sphinxis* Roelofs, 1875

pubescens Roelofs, 1875 – PRIM.

Subtribe Styphlina Jekel, 1861

Genus *Paraphilernus* Desbrochers des Loges, 1892

bilunulatus (Desbrochers des Loges, 1870) – TMN, KURG, NOV.

Genus *Philernus* Schoenherr, 1835

cretaceous Korotyayev, 1979 – RAL, TUV.

farinosus (Gebler, 1829) – “ALT” (Heyden 1880-1881), “Ostsibirien” (Klima 1934b).

Genus *Pseudostyphlus* Tournier, 1874

orthochaetinus Reitter, 1916 – ALT.

pillumus (Gyllenhal, 1835) – TMN, CHEL.

Tribe Acalyptini Thomson, 1859

Subtribe Acalyptina Thomson, 1859

Genus *Acalyptus* Schoenherr, 1833

caprini (Fabricius, 1792) – YAN, KHM, TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, KHA, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

sericeus Gyllenhal, 1835 – KHM, TMN, KURG, NOV, KEM, ALT, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, PRIM.

Tribe Anthonomini Thomson, 1859

Genus *Anthonomus* Germar, 1817

Subgenus *Anthonomidius* Reitter, 1915

dauricus Faust, 1891 – CHT, AMUR, Khab, PRIM.

=*dilutus* Reitter, 1915

morosus Faust, 1891 – ALT, RAL, KHA, TUV.

Subgenus *Anthonomorphus* Weise, 1883

lukjanovitschi Ter-Minassian, 1948 – PRIM.

phyllocola (Herbst, 1795) – KHM, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, TUV, CHT, PRIM, KUR.

[*pinivorax* Silfvenberg, 1977 – records of this species from “Khab, PRIM” (Egorov 1976b) are wrong].

Subgenus *Anthonomus* s. str.

aino Kono, 1939 – PRIM.

bisignifer Schenkling, 1874 – AMUR, Khab, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

conspersus Desbrochers des Loges, 1868 – TMN, KEM, RAL, TUV, IRK, PRIM.

cribratellus Reitter, 1915 – Khab, PRIM.

incurvus (Panzer, 1795) – CHEL, KURG, KEM, RAL, KHA, IRK, “Khab” (Dieckmann 1968)].

=*humeralis* Panzer, 1795

pedicularis (Linnaeus, 1758) – ALT, KEM, TUV, IRK, AMUR, Khab, PRIM, “Transbaicalia” (Egorov 1976b).

pomorum (Linnaeus, 1758) – IRK, AMUR, Khab, PRIM, KUR.

[*pyri* Kollar, 1837 – record of this species from “Siberia” (Winkler 1930-1932) is wrong].

rubi rubi (Herbst, 1795) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, TMN, OMS, TOM.

rubi terreus Gyllenhal, 1836 – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, AMUR, Khab, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

=*czekanovskii* Ter-Minassian, 1936

semenovi Ter-Minassian, 1948 – PRIM.

sorbi Germar, 1821 – “YAK, MAG, Khab, PRIM, SAKH” (Egorov 1976b; Egorov and Basarukina 1981).

yuasai Kono, 1939 – Khab, PRIM.

Insertae sedis

laticornis Pic, 1902 – “Siberia” (Winkler 1930-1932).

Subgenus *Furcipes* Desbrochers des Loges, 1868

rectirostris (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Subgenus *Pterochalybs* Ter-Minassian, 1936

reichardti Ter-Minassian, 1948 – KHAB, PRIM.

subchalybaeus Reitter, 1915 – KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Bradybatus* Germar, 1823

Subgenus *Bradybatus* s. str.

limbatus Roelofs, 1875 – KHAB, PRIM, KUR.

sharpi Tournier, 1873 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, KUR, “E Siberia” (Egorov 1976b).

Genus *Brachonyx* Schoenherr, 1825

pineti (Paykull, 1792) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, PRIM.

Tribe Curculionini Latreille, 1802

Subtribe Curculionina Latreille, 1802

Genus *Curculio* Linnaeus, 1758

aino (Kono, 1930) – KHAB, PRIM, KUR.

albiquama Ter-Minassian, 1956 – “PRIM” (Egorov et al. 1996).

alboscuteclatus (Roelofs, 1875) – “PRIM” (Egorov 1976b).

amurensis Heller, 1927 – KHAB, PRIM.

betulae (Stephens, 1831) – TMN, TMN, NOV, KEM, ALT, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT.
=*cerasorum* Paykull, 1792

=*budjumkanensis* Legalov, 2007, **syn. nov.** [Mr. Yutaka Notsu (Japan, Kanagawa) drew my attention to the similarity of *C. budjumkanensis* to *C. betulae*. They belong to the same species, and the differences are variability.].

conjugalis (Faust, 1882) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

convexus (Roelofs, 1875) – PRIM.

dentipes (Roelofs, 1875) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

=*arakawai* Matsumura et Kono, 1928

dieckmanni (Faust, 1887) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

distinguendus (Roelofs, 1875) – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov 1976b).

flavescens (Roelofs, 1875) – “Russia” (Pelsue and Zhang 2000).

fordi Pelsue et Zhang, 2002 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

fluvipennis Morimoto, 1960 – PRIM.

funebri (Roelofs, 1875) – “KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR” (Egorov et al. 1996).

glandium Marsham, 1802 – TMN.

koreanus Heller, 1927 – AMUR, PRIM.

robustus (Roelofs, 1875) – “Russia” (Pelsue and Zhang 2000).
rubidus (Gyllenhal, 1835) – TMN, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT.
sikkimensis (Heller, 1927) – PRIM.
styracis (Roelofs, 1875) – “KHAB, PRIM” (Egorov and Kabakov 1976).
ussuriensis Heller, 1927 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.
villosus Fabricius, 1871 – “PRIM” (Egorov 1976b).

Subtribe Archariina Pelsue et O'Brien, 2011

Genus *Archarius* Gistel, 1856

Subgenus *Archarius* s. str.

salicivorus (Paykull, 1792) – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.
 =*parasiticus* Morimoto, 1962, **syn. nov.** [*Curculio parasiticus* has no significant differences from *A. salicivorus*]

Subgenus *Balanobius* Jekel, 1861

exiguus (Kwon et Lee, 1990) – PRIM.
crux (Fabricius, 1777) – OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, BUR, CHT, KAM, AMUR.
latispiculum (Kwon et Lee, 1990) – PRIM.
 =*parvus* Kwon et Lee, 1990
pictus (Roelofs, 1875) – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Subgenus *Toptaria* Kwon et Lee, 1990

roelofsi (Heller, 1927) – PRIM, SAKH.

Genus *Koreoculio* Kwon et Lee, 1990

minitissimus (Dalla Torre et Schenkling, 1932) – PRIM.

Genus *Pagumia* Kwon et Lee, 1990

changeoni Kwon et Lee, 1990 – PRIM.

Tribe Rhamphini Rafinesque, 1815

Subtribe Rhamphina Rafinesque, 1815

Genus *Isochnus* Thomson, 1859

angustifrons (West, 1917) – KHM (Gratshev 2015).
arcticus (Korotyaev, 1977) – YAN, KRN, CHUK.
flagellum (Erichson, 1902) – YAN, TMN, TOM, NOV, ALT, RAL, TUV, KHAB, PRIM, CHUK.
kamchaticus Morimoto, 2000 – “KAM” (Morimoto 2000).

sequensi (Stierlin, 1894) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, IRK, BUR, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

=*populicola* Silfverberg, 1977

Genus *Orchestes* Illiger, 1798

Subgenus *Alyctus* Thomson, 1859

aterrimus (Roelofs, 1875) – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

calceatus (Germar, 1821) – YAN, KHM, TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

galloisi Kono, 1930 – “KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR” (Egorov et al. 1996).

jozanus Kono, 1930 – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov et al. 1996).

matsumuranus Kono, 1930 – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov et al. 1996).

rusci (Herbst, 1795) – YAN, KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

[*testaceus* (Mueller, 1776) – records of this species from Asia need confirmation].

Subgenus *Amurorchestes* Legalov, 2007

koltzei Faust, 1882 – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Subgenus *Granulorchestes* Legalov, 2007

fasciculatus Faust, 1882 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

Subgenus *Orchestes* s. str.

amplithorax Faust, 1882 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

amurensis Faust, 1887 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, KUR.

excellens Roelofs, 1874 – “AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR” (Egorov et al. 1996).

hortorum (Fabricius, 1792) – “ALT” (Heyden 1880-1881).

=*avellanae* Donovan, 1797

hustachei Klima, 1920 – PRIM, KUR.

jota (Fabricius, 1787) – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

lateritius (Morimoto, 1984) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

mutabilis Boheman, 1843 – IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

=*variegatus* Roelofs, 1875

=*spinosus* Hustache, 1920

nitens (Morimoto, 1984) – PRIM.

nomizo (Kono, 1930) – “KAM, SAKH, KUR” (Korotyaev 1992a).

[*quendenfeldti* (Gerhardt, 1865) – record of this species from “PRIM” (Egorov 1976b) is wrong].

ruber (Ter-Minassian, 1953) – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

sanguinipes Roelofs, 1875 – PRIM.

scitus Faust, 1887 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, “Transbaicalia” (Egorov et al. 1996).

similis Faust, 1882 – PRIM.

sparsus Fahraeus, 1843 – KHM, PRIM, KUR.

steppensis Korotyaev, 2016 – CHEL, KHA, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, KHAB, PRIM.

subbifasciatus Faust, 1882 – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Pseudorchestes* Bedel, 1894

asiaticus Legalov, 1997 – CHEL, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL.

pratensis (Germar, 1821) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)

Genus *Rhamphus* Clairville, 1798

Subgenus *Rhamphus* s. str.

choseniae Korotyaev, 1984 – KAM, MAG.

oxyacanthae (Marsham, 1802) – BUR.

pulicarius (Herbst, 1795) – TMN, NOV, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Subgenus *Trichorhamphus* Korotyaev, 1984

hisamatsui Chujo et Morimoto, 1960 – MAG, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Rhynchaenus* Clairville, 1798

Subgenus *Rhynchaenus* s. str.

medvedevi Korotyaev, 1995 – BUR.

pacificus (Faust, 1887) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

xylostei Clairville 1798 – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.

Genus *Tachyerges* Schoenherr, 1825

dauricus (Faust, 1882) – BUR, CHT, AMUR, PRIM.

decoratus (Germar, 1821) – NOV, CHIT, AMUR, PRIM.

parvicollis (LeConte, 1876) – “YAK” (Averensky 2003b).

pseudostigma (Tempere, 1982) – TOM, NOV, KEM, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, PRIM.

rufitarsis (Germar, 1827) – NOV, IRK, YAK, PRIM.

salicis (Linnaeus, 1758) – YAN, TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

stigma (Germar, 1821) – YAN, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, CHT, YAK, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Tribe Tychiini Thomson, 1859

Subtribe Tychiina Thomson, 1859

Genus *Sibinia* Germar, 1817

Subgenus *Dichotychius* Bedel, 1885

beckeri Desbrochers des Loges, 1873 – TMN, OMS, NOV, ALT, TUV, CHT.

staticis (Becker, 1864) – ALT.

Subgenus *Sibinia* s. str.

annulifera Pic, 1902 – NOV, TUV, IRK, CHT, AMUR, Khab, PRIM.

elliptica Korotyaev et Egorov, 1996 – PRIM.

femoralis Germar, 1823 – ALT, AMUR, PRIM.

hopffgarteni Tournier, 1874 – CHEL, NOV, KRN, TUV, IRK, CHT, AMUR.

pelluscens (Scopoli, 1772) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.

[*planiuscula* (Desbrochers des Loges, 1873) – record of this species from “Siberia” (Winkler 1930-1932) is wrong].

subelliptica Desbrochers des Loges, 1873 – CHEL, NOV, KRN, TUV, CHT, PRIM.

tibialis (Gyllenhal, 1835) – CHEL, OMS, NOV, ALT, KEM, KRN, IRK, CHT, PRIM.

unicolor (Fahraeus, 1843) – CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, TUV, CHT.

ussurica Korotyaev et Egorov, 1996 – PRIM.

viscaria (Linnaeus, 1761) – TMN, CHEL, NOV, ALT, PRIM.

vittata Germar, 1823 – CHEL, NOV.

Genus *Tychius* Germar, 1817

Subgenus *Lepidotychius* Penecke, 1922

crassifemoris Bajtenov, 1977 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

[*morawitzi* Beck, 1864 – record of this species from “Siberia” (Winkler 1930-1932) belongs to Kazakhstan].

alexii (Korotyaev, 1991) – KRN.

Subgenus *Tychius* s. str.

albolineatus Motschulsky, 1860 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, NOV, KEM, RAL, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, PRIM, KUR.

[*alhagi* (Faust, 1884) – record of this species from “Sib.or.” (Winkler 1930-1932) is wrong].

astragali Becker, 1862 – ALT.

aureolus Kiesenwetter, 1852 – TMN, CHEL, OMS, NOV, ALT.

beckeri Tournier, 1874 – ALT.

breviusculus Desbrochers des Loges, 1873 – CHEL, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, IRK, BUR, YAK, PRIM.

crassirostris (Kirsch, 1871) – NOV, ALT, AMUR, PRIM.

flavus Becker, 1864 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, NOV, ALT, KEM, “E Siberia” (Dieckmann 1988).

- hauseri* Faust, 1889 – RAL.
junceus (Reich, 1797) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, ALT.
kerulensis (Bajtenov, 1981) – CHT.
krausei Caldara, 1985 – NOV, KEM, RAL, IRK, AMUR, PRIM.
lineatulus Stephens, 1831 – TMN.
longulus Desbrochers des Loges, 1873 – CHEL, TUV, BUR.
medicaginis Ch. Brisout de Barneville, 1863 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.
meliloti Stephens, 1831 – TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, TUV, IRK, BUR.
oriens Hoffmann, 1964 – KHA.
ovalis Roelofs, 1875 – CHT, AMUR, PRIM.
picirostris (Fabricius, 1787) – TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, ALT, KEM, IRK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
praescutellaris (Pic, 102) – TUV, CHT.
quinquepunctatus obscuripes Korotyaev, 1996 – OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, TUV, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.
quinquepunctatus quinquepunctatus (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, CHEL, KURG.
sharpi Tournier, 1873 – CHEL.
squamulatus Gyllenhal, 1835 – “RAL” (Dieckmann 1988).
stephensi Schoenherr, 1835 – TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA.
subsulcatus Tournier, 1874 – CHEL, OMS, NOV, ALT.
tectus LeConte, 1876 – OMS, TOM, NOV, RAL, KHA, TUV, KRN, IRK, BUR, YAK, CHUK, KAM, MAG, PRIM.
tridentinus Penecke, 1922 – CHEL.
trivialis Boheman, 1843 – CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK.
uralensis Pic, 1902 – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, TUV, CHT.

Tribe Cionini Schoenherr, 1825

Genus *Cionus* Clairville, 1798

- gebleri* Gyllenhal, 1838 – NOV, ALT, RAL, KEM.
 [*helleri* Reitter, 1904 – This species is absent in Russia].
hortulanus (Geoffroy, 1785) – KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV.
latefasciatus Voss, 1956 – PRIM
longicollis Ch. Brisout de Barneville, 1863 – TMN, NOV, KEM.
nigritarsis Reitter, 1904 – TMN, ALT.
scrophulariae (Linnaeus, 1758) – TOM, ALT.
tamazo Kono, 1930 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
thapsus thapsus (Fabricius, 1792) – KURG, ALT.
tuberculosis (Scopoli, 1763) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, KHA.
zonovi Korotyaev, 1984 – TUV.

Genus *Stereonychidius* Morimoto, 1962

galloisi (Hustache, 1920) – PRIM.

Genus *Stereonychus* Suffrian, 1854

[*fraxini* (DeGeer, 1775) – record of this species from “PRIM” (Egorov 1976b) is wrong].

japonicus Hustache, 1920 – PRIM.

marinae Legalov et Reshetnikov, 2020 – PRIM.

thoracicus Faust, 1887 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, KUR, “E Siberia” (Egorov 1976b).

Tribe Mecinini Gistel, 1856

Genus *Cleopomiarus* Pierce, 1919

distinctus (Boheman, 1845) – TOM, NOV, KEM, PRIM.

= *dictamnophilus* Zherichin, 1996

flavoscutellatus (Morimoto, 1959) – PRIM.

= *tapirus* Korotyaev, 1999

graminis (Gyllenhal, 1813) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

kobanzo (Kono, 1930) – KHAB, PRIM.

[*longirostris* (Gyllenhal, 1837) – record of this species from “PRIM” (Egorov 1976b) is wrong].

mandschuricus (Voss, 1952) – PRIM.

vestitus (Roelofs, 1875) – CHT, AMUR, PRIM.

Genus *Gymnetron* Schoenherr, 1825

beccabungae (Linnaeus, 1760) – TMN, NOV.

desbrochersi Reitter, 1907 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)

melanarium (Germar, 1821) – NOV, KEM.

miyoshii Miyoshi, 1922 – “TUV” (Caldara 2008).

terminassianae Smreczynsky, 1975 – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, PRIM.

veronicae (Germar, 1821) – CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL.

villosipenne Roelofs, 1875 – “AMUR, KHAB, PRIM” (Caldara 2008).

villosulum Gyllenhal, 1838 – ALT, CHEL.

Genus *Mecinus* Germar, 1821

collaris Germar, 1821 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, NOV, CHT, AMUR, PRIM.

heydeni Wencker, 1866 – TMN, NOV, KEM.

janthinus Germar, 1821 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, IRK.

pascuorum (Gyllenhal, 1813) – “E Siberia, Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

plantaginis (Eppelsheim, 1875) – TMN, CHEL, NOV, KEM, ALT.

zherichini (Korotyaev, 1995) – IRK, CHT, PRIM.

Genus *Miarus* Schoenherr, 1826

ajugae (Herbst, 1795) – CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, IRK, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

atricolor Morimoto, 1983 – RAL, CHT, PRIM.

Genus *Rhinusa* Stephens, 1829**Subgenus *Eutemnoscelus* Desbrochers des Loges, 1893**

linariae (Panzer, 1792) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM.

Subgenus *Rhinusa* Stephens, 1829

antirrhini (Paykull, 1800) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, TUV, IRK, CHT, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

brisouti (Faust, 1891) – CHT.

eversmanni (Rosenschold, 1838) – NOV, KEM, ALT.

pilosa (Gyllenhal, 1838) – NOV, KEM.

neta (Germar, 1821) – TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, IRK, CHT.

soluta (Faust, 1891) – “Sib. or.” (Winkler 1930-1932).

tetra (Fabricius, 1792) – CHEL, ALT.

Tribe *Smicronychini* Seidlitz, 1891**Genus *Sharpia* Tournier, 1873**

[*heydeni* Tournier, 1874 – record of this species from “Sib. or.” (Winkler 1930-1932) is wrong].

[*inconspicua* Faust, 1881 – record of this species from “Sib. or.” (Winkler 1930-1932) is wrong].

Genus *Smicronyx* Schoenherr, 1843**Subgenus *Smicronyx* s. str.**

coecus (Reich, 1797) – TMN, NOV.

jungermaniae (Reich, 1797) – ALT.

madaranus Kono, 1930 – AMUR, PRIM.

rubricatus Kono, 1930 – AMUR, PRIM.

smreczynskii F. Solari, 1952 – ALT, “KEM, TUV” (Krivets and Korotyaev 1998).

[*swertae* Voss, 1953 – record of this species from “Siberia” (Egorov 1976b) is wrong].

Tribe *Ochyromerini* Voss, 1935**Genus *Ochyromera* Pascoe, 1874**

suturalis Kojima et Morimoto, 1996 – KHAB, PRIM.

Subfamily Cyclominae Schoenherr, 1826

Tribe Hipporhinini Lacordaire, 1863

Genus *Borborocoetes* Schoenherr, 1842

signatipes Faust, 1883 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

Genus *Gronops* Schoenherr, 1823

Subgenus *Asperogronops* Solari, 1940

inaequalis (Boheman, 1842) – TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, PRIM.

semenovi (Faust, 1890) – TUV, BUR.

sibiricus (Allard, 1870) – TUV, BUR, CHT.

sulcatus Boheman, 1842 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

Subgenus *Pseudogronops* F. Solari, 1940

angusticollis (Boheman, 1845) – “Daurien” (Schenkling and Marshall 1929).

Tribe Notiomimetini Wollaston, 1873

Genus *Isonycholips* Chujo et Voss, 1960

gotoi Chujo et Voss, 1960 – PRIM, KUR.

Subfamily Entiminnæ Schoenherr, 1823

Supertribe Entimintæ Schoenherr, 1823

Tribe Tropiphorini Marseul, 1863

Subtribe Strangalioididina Lacordaire, 1863

Genus *Dyslobus* LeConte, 1869

variegatum (Motschulsky, 1845) – TMN, KAM, MAG, AMUR, Khab, PRIM, SAKH.

Genus *Graptus* Schoenherr, 1823

[*triguttatus triguttatus* (Fabricius, 1775) – “RAL” (Davidian and Arzanov 2004)].

Genus *Trichalophus* LeConte, 1876

albonotatus (Motschulsky, 1860) – IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, Khab, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

=*quadrinotatus* Motschulsky, 1860

=*rubripes* Reitter, 1913

=*rubripes* Zherikhin et Nazarov, 1990

biguttatus (Gebler, 1832) – KEM, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR.

=*rudis* Boheman, 1840

=*korotyaevi* Zherichin et Nazarov, 1990

boeberi (Schoenherr, 1826) – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN.

=*leucon* Gebler, 1834

[*humeralis* (Gebler, 1834) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

[*juldusanus* Reitter, 1913 – records of this species from “Altai” (Winkler 1932; Klima 1935) belong to East-Kazakhstan Prov.].

maeklini (Faust, 1890) – YAN, KEM, RAL, KHA, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

quadriguttatus (Gebler, 1829) – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA.

[*vittatus* (Faust, 1882) – record of this species from “RAL” (Legalov 2010a) belongs to Mongolian Altai].

Insertae sedis

inermis Reitter, 1913 – “PRIM” (Egorov 1976b).

Genus *Xeralophus* Korotyaev, 1991

cretaceous (Reitter, 1894) – TUV.

Subtribe *Byrsopagina* Lacordaire, 1863

Genus *Byrsopages* Schoenherr, 1842

dissimilis (Faust, 1894) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

sachalinensis Egorov, 1976 – SAKH.

villosus Boheman, 1842 – KAM, KUR.

Genus *Lepidophorus* Kirby, 1837

lineaticollis Kirby, 1837 – CHUK.

Genus *Vitavitus* Kissinger, 1974

thulius Kissinger, 1974 – “CHUK (?) , MAG (?)” (Egorov et al. 1996).

Tribe *Ophryastini* Lacordaire, 1863

Subtribe *Deracanthina* Legalov, 2020

Genus *Deracanthus* Schoenherr, 1826

Subgenus *Deracanthus* s. str.

inderiensis (Pallas, 1771) – “RAL” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

[*sibiricus* (Thunberg, 1799) – record of this species from “Siberia” (Schenkling and Marshall 1931) belongs to Kazakhstan].

Supertribe Hyperitae Lacordaire, 1863

Tribe Hyperini Lacordaire, 1863

Subtribe Cepurina Capiomont, 1867

Genus *Fronto* Petri, 1901

= *Parahypera* Brancsik, 1914

capiomonti (Faust, 1882) – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

= *ussurica* Brancsik, 1914

Subtribe Coniatina Legalov, 2007

Genus *Coniatus* Germar, 1817

minutus Korotyaev, 1984 – TUV.

[*splendidulus* (Fabricius, 1781) – record of this species from “Siberia” (Csiki 1934b) is wrong].

Subtribe Macrotarrhusina Legalov, 2007

Genus *Alexiola* Suvorov, 1912

Subgenus *Alexiola* s. str.

argenteomontanus (Korotyaev, 1995) – TUV.

[*cuprifer* (Petri, 1901) – record of this species from “Altai” (Csiki 1934b) belongs to Kazakhstan].

validirostris (Faust, 1890) – TUV.

Genus *Asiodonus* Legalov, 2010, stat. res.

[The statuses of several Hyperini taxa are restored according by Legalov (2011)].

belokobyskyi Legalov, 2011 – PRIM.

burjaticus (Korotyaev, 1998) – BUR.

hertshensis (Legalov, 2009) – TUV.

knutelskyi Legalov, 2012 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

mniszewski (Capiomont, 1867) – ALT, RAL.

opanassenkoi (Legalov, 1997) – NOV, RAL, KHA, KRN.

rugulosus (Petri, 1901) – PRIM.

sajanicus (Korotyaev, 1998) – RAL, KHA, KRN, TUV.

shokhrini Legalov, 2012 – PRIM.

sikhotealinensis Legalov, 2018 – KHAB.

streltzovi Legalov, 2012 – AMUR.

Genus *Donus* Jekel, 1865

cupreus (Legalov, 1997) – RAL.

dauci (Olivier, 1808) – TMN, KURG, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL.

dudkoi (Legalov, 1999) – KHA.

lepidus (Capiomont, 1868) – TOM, KEM, RAL, KRN, CHT.

Genus *Eremochorus* Zaslavskij, 1962**Subgenus *Eremochorus* s. str.**

aterrimus Korotyaev, 1995 – TUV.

[*concinnus* (Boheman, 1842) – record of this species from “Siberia” (Csiki 1934b) belongs to Kazakhstan].

gebleri (Gebler, 1833) – “Kolyvan” (Heyden 1880-1881)

[*elongatus* (Petri, 1901) – record of this species from “Altai” (Winkler 1932) belongs to Kazakhstan].

faldermanni Boheman, 1840 – RAL.

inflatus (Petri, 1901) – RAL, TUV.

[*kolbei* (Petri, 1901) – record of this species from “Siberia” (Csiki 1934b) belongs to Kazakhstan].

michailovi Legalov, 2007 – RAL.

[*motschulskyi* (Boheman, 1842) – record of this species from “Altai” (Heyden 1880-1881) belongs to Kazakhstan].

[*similis* (Petri, 1903) – record of this species from “Siberia” (Csiki 1934b) belongs to Kazakhstan].

shevnini Legalov, 2011 – RAL.

Subgenus *Proeremochorus* Legalov, 2010

mongolicus (Motschulsky, 1860) – TUV, Khab.

sinuaticollis (Faust, 1890) – RAL.

zaslavskii Korotyaev, 1995 – TUV.

Genus *Metadonus* Capiomont, 1868

anceps (Boheman, 1842) – OMS, ALT, RAL, TUV.

curtus (Boheman, 1842) – ALT, KHA, “W Siberia, Transbaicalia” (Csiki 1934b).

distinguendus (Boheman, 1842) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, Khab, PRIM, SAKH.

incitus (Boheman, 1842) – RAL, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT.

Genus *Oreochorus* Zaslavki et Korotyaev, 1998

dervizi Korotyaev, 1998 – TUV.

Genus *Pachypera* Capiomont, 1868

deportata (Boheman, 1842) – NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA.

Genus *Sibirodonus* Legalov, 2010, stat. res.

scapularis (Gebler, 1833) – BUR, CHT, “W Siberia” (Csiki 1934b).

Subtribe Hyperina Marseul, 1863

Genus *Boreohypera* Korotyaev, 1999, stat. res.

diversipunctata (Schrank, 1798) – YAN, KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, KRN, TUV, CHUK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

graeseri (Faust, 1887) – TOM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

kirejtshuki Legalov, 2011 – ALT.

tuvensis Legalov, 2011 – KRN, TUV.

Genus *Eririnomorphus* Capiomont, 1868, stat. res.

arundinis (Paykull, 1792) – TMN, ALT.

rumicis (Linnaeus, 1758) – KHM, TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, IRK, YAK, KAM, MAG, CHUK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Hypera* Germar, 1817

Subgenus *Dapalinus* Capiomont, 1868

forficata (Penecke, 1928) – TMN, CHEL.

meles (Fabricius, 1792) – TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Subgenus *Hypera* s. str.

denominanda (Capiomont, 1868) – TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.

nigrirostris (Fabricius, 1775) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, IRK, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

ornata (Capiomont, 1868) – YAN, TOM, NOV, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, CHT, YAK, CHUK, AMUR, KHAB.

sagittata (Zaslavskij, 1966) – CHT, PRIM.

miles (Paykull, 1792) – KHM, TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

transsylvanica (Petri, 1901) – TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK.

viciae (Gyllenhal, 1813) – TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, KRN, TUV, IRK, YAK, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

Subgenus *Kippenbergia* Alonso-Zarazaga, 2005

arator (Linnaeus, 1785) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, AMUR, PRIM.

misella (Faust, 1882) – TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Limobius* Schoenherr, 1843

borealis borealis (Paykull, 1792) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, IRK.

Genus *Zaslavskypera* Legalov, 2011, stat. res.

adpersiformis (Reitter, 1915) – TOM, NOV, KEM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

conmaculata (Herbst 1795) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, KUR.

interruptovittata (Desbrochers des Loges, 1875) – KEM, KRN.

libanotidis (Reitter, 1896) – NOV, ALT.

Supertribe Otiorhynchitae Schoenherr, 1826**Tribe Phyllobiini Schoenherr, 1826****Genus *Phyllobius* Germar, 1823****Subgenus *Alsus* Motschulsky, 1845**

brevis Gyllenhal, 1834 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KHA, IRK, BUR, CHT.

Subgenus *Angarophyllobius* Korotyaev et Egorov, 1977

baicalicus Korotyaev, 1979 – IRK.

claviger Faust, 1889 – PRIM.

femoralis Boheman, 1842 – RAL, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

fumigatus Boheman, 1842 – ALT, RAL, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

hochhuthi Faust, 1883 – BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

kaszabi L. Arnoldi et Korotyaev, 1977 – TUV.

kolymensis Korotyaev et Egorov, 1977 – MAG.

logunovi Korotyaev, 1995 – TUV.

lukjanovitshi Korotyaev et Egorov, 1977 – KHA.

maculosus Motschulsky, 1860 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

mongolicus Korotyaev et Egorov, 1977 – TUV, IRK, BUR.

profanus Faust, 1881 – KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK.

sahlbergi Faust, 1890 – KRN.

sheri Kuzmina et Korotyaev, 2019 – YAK (?).

svetlanae Korotyaev et Egorov, 1977 – KRN, TUV, IRK, YAK.

tuvensis Korotyaev et Egorov, 1977 – TUV.

verae Korotyaev, 1984 – TUV.

virens (Faust, 1890) – KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, YAK.

Subgenus *Aprepes* Schoenherr, 1847

altaicus Gebler, 1833 – TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA.

crassus crassus Motschulsky, 1860 – KEM, IRK, YAK.

crassus platyomus Korotyaev et Egorov, 1977 – RAL, TUV.

Subgenus *Dieletus* Reitter, 1916

argentatus argentatus (Linnaeus, 1758) – “KURG” (Redicortsev 1908), “OMS” (Lavrov 1927).

Subgenus *Metaphyllobius* Smirnov, 1913

glaucus (Scopoli, 1763) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)

litoralis Faust, 1887 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

obovatus Gebler, 1834 – KHM, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA.

pomaceus Gyllenhal, 1834 – YAN, KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK.

= *fessus* Boheman, 1843

Subgenus *Nanoschetus* Reitter, 1916

cylindricollis Gyllenhal, 1834 – TMN, CHEL, NOV.

Subgenus *Nemoicus* Dillwyn, 1829

oblongus (Linnaeus, 1758) – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.

Subgenus *Nipponophyllobius* Korotyaev et Egorov, 1977

picipes Motschulsky, 1861 – SAKH, KUR.

Subgenus *Odontophyllobius* Pesarini, 1968

armatus Roelofs, 1876 – KUR.

Subgenus *Otophyllobius* Pesarini, 1968

prolongatus Motschulsky, 1866 – SAKH, KUR.

Subgenus *Parnemoicus* Schilsky, 1911

viridicollis (Fabricius, 1792) – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL.

Subgenus *Phyllobius* s. str.

pyri (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, TUV, IRK, PRIM.

thalassinus Gyllenhal, 1834 – KHM, TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, YAK.

Subgenus *Pterygorrhynchus* Pesarini, 1969

contemptus Schoenherr, 1832 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.

crassipes Motschulsky, 1860 – TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

maculicornis (Germar, 1823) – YAN, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK.
zherichini Korotyaev et Egorov, 1977 – PRIM.

Subgenus *Subphyllobius* Schilsky, 1911

viridiaeris viridiaeris (Laicharting, 1781) – YAN, KHM, TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, CHUK, KAM, MAG, AMUR, Khab, PRIM, SAKH.

Tribe Otiorhynchini Schoenherr, 1826

Genus *Otiorhynchus* Germar, 1822

Subgenus *Altaivagus* L. Arnoldi, 1975

unctuosus Germar, 1823 – TMN, CHEL, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA.

Subgenus *Amosilnus* Reitter, 1913

grandineus Germar, 1823 – KHM, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, KRN, IRK, BUR, PRIM.

=*buchtarmensis* Bajtenov, 1977, **syn. nov.**

=*rhododendroni* Bajtenov, 1977, **syn. nov.**

oberti (Faust, 1887) – TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN, IRK.

Insertae sedis

dauricus Stierlin, 1862 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

[*simulans* Stierlin, 1877 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Subgenus *Arammichnus* Gozis, 1882

[*cribricollis* Gyllenhal, 1834 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Subgenus *Choilisanus* Reitter, 1912

raucus (Fabricius, 1777) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.

velutinus Germar, 1823 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT, KHA.

=*simplex* Stierlin, 1881

Subgenus *Cryphiphorus* Stierlin, 1861

ligustici (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, NOV, ALT.

Subgenus *Ditrichosomus* L. Arnoldi, 1975

improbus L. Arnoldi, 1975 – RAL, TUV.

Subgenus *Holomrasus* Reitter, 1912

= *Trichosmobodes* L. Arnoldi, 1975, **syn. nov.**

[The subgenera differ in the shape of the eyes, but the species which belong to them are very close].

obscurus Gyllenhal, 1834 – NOV, ALT, KRN.

= *perplexus* Gyllenhal, 1834, **syn. nov.** [Male and female were described as different species].

ongon Alonso-Zarazaga, 2013 – RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK.

= *hispidus* Stierlin, 1886

subocularis L. Arnoldi, 1975 – OMS, NOV.

sushkini L. Arnoldi, 1975 – RAL.

Subgenus *Magnanotius* Alonso-Zarazaga et Lyal, 2002

[*equestris* (Richter, 1820) – record of this species from W Siberia (Bajtenov 1974) belongs to *O. grandineus*].

Subgenus *Nehrodistus* Reitter, 1912

[*turca* Boheman, 1842 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Subgenus *Mitomiris* Reitter, 1912

[*esau* Stierlin, 1883 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

[*furiosus* Reitter, 1916 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Subgenus *Otiolehus* Reitter, 1914

tristis (Scopoli, 1763) – YAN, KHM, TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, ALT, IRK.

Subgenus *Otiorrhynchus* s. str.

concinus Gyllenhal, 1834 – CHEL, record of this species from Altai (Heyden 1880–1881) belongs to *O. wittmeri*].

[*lirus* Schoenherr, 1834 – “SW Siberia” (Arnoldi et al. 1974)].

= *laevigatus* Fabricius, 1792

wittmeri Legalov, 1999 – TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL.

Subgenus *Pinduchus* Reitter, 1912

tarphiderus Reitter, 1914 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

Subgenus *Podonebistus* Reitter, 1912

[*bardus* Boheman, 1842 – “Altai (Bajtenov, 1974)”.]

= *altaicus* Stierlin, 1861

= *karkaralensis* Bajtenov, 1974

= *relicinus* Arnoldi, 1975

janovskii Korotyayev, 1990 – RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV.

ursus Gebler, 1844 – ALT.

= *kasachstanicus* Arnoldi, 1964

Subgenus *Postaremus* Reitter, 1912*nodosus* (Müller, 1764) – YAN, KHM.**Subgenus *Dibredus* Reitter, 1912**[*laeviusculus* Stierlin, 1861 – “Siberia” (Winkler, 1930-1932)].**Subgenus *Mongolorrhynchus* L. Arnoldi, 1975***mordkovitshi* L. Arnoldi, 1975 – TUV.*rectipilosus* L. Arnoldi, 1975 – RAL.*tuvensis* Korotyaev, 1995 – TUV.**Subgenus *Nubidanus* Reitter, 1912**

Insertae sedis

marseuli (Stierlin, 1872) – “Altai” (Winkler 1930-1932).**Subgenus *Osmobodes* Reitter, 1912***beatus* Faust, 1890 – RAL, KRN, TUV.*brevilatus* L. Arnoldi, 1975 – KRN, TUV.*confluens* Reitter, 1912 – KHA, KRN.*cribrosicollis* Boheman, 1842 – IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR.*khentejensis* L. Arnoldi, 1975 – TUV.*mongolicus* Reitter, 1912 – IRK, BUR.*streblhoffi* Stierlin, 1880 – RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR.

Insertae sedis

curvimanus Reitter, 1912 – “Baical” (Winkler 1930-1932).*innocuus* Boheman, 1842 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).*tenuimanus* Faust, 1890 – “Sib. oc.” (Winkler 1930-1932).*venalis* Faust, 1888 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).**Subgenus *Podoropelmus* Reitter, 1912***fullo* (Schrank, 1781) – TMN, ALT.*rotundus* Marseul, 1872 – NOV, OMS, IRK.=*smreczynskii* Cmoluch, 1968**Subgenus *Pendragon* Gozis, 1885***kuraicus* Korotyaev, 1998 – RAL.*ovatus ovatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) – KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, KRN, IRK, BUR, YAK, SAKH.**Subgenus *Prototis* L. Arnoldi, 1975***michnoi* Korotyaev, 1996 – BUR.*popovi* Faust, 1888 – IRK, BUR.

Subgenus *Pseudocryphiphorus* Magnano, 1998

chrysostrictus Gyllenhal, 1834 – CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, ALT.

= *conspersus* Herbst, 1795

pullus Gyllenhal, 1834 – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, KRN.

= *irritabilis* Faust, 1887

Subgenus *Stupamacus* Reitter, 1912

politus Gyllenhal, 1834 – KHM, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, YAK.

proletarius Boheman, 1842 – “Sib. oc.” (Heyden 1880-1881).

scintillus Reitter, 1912 – “Altai” (Heyden 1880-1881; Bajtenov 1974).

supremus Reitter, 1912 – “Altai” (Heyden 1880-1881; Bajtenov 1974).

Genus *Parameira* Seidlitz, 1868

Subgenus *Stierlinia* Desbrochers des Loges, 1909

gebleri Faust, 1893 – TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, CHT, YAK.

Supertribe Cyphiceritae Lacordaire, 1863

Tribe Metacinopini Reitter, 1913

Genus *Pseudomylocerus* Desbrochers des Loges, 1873

dorsalis (Mannerheim, 1825) – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL.

Tribe Cyphicerini Lacordaire, 1863

Subtribe Cyphicerina Lacordaire, 1863

Genus *Anosimus* Roelofs, 1873

fasciatus (Faust, 1887) – PRIM.

Genus *Corigetus* Desbrochers des Loges, 1872

marmoratus Desbrochers des Loges, 1873 – IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR.

Genus *Cyphicerinus* Marshal, 1928

czerskii Zherichin, 1991 – PRIM.

Genus *Ptochidius* Motschulsky, 1858

tesselatus (Motschulsky, 1860) – CHT, AMUR, Khab, PRIM, SAKH.

Subtribe Acanthotrachelina Marshall, 1944

Genus *Calomycterus* Roelofs, 1873

setarius Roelofs, 1873 – PRIM.

Subtribe Myllocerina Pierce, 1913**Genus *Corymacronus* Kojima et Morimoto, 2006***costulatus* (Motschulsky, 1860) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.**Genus *Eumyllocerus* Sharp, 1896***gratiosus* Sharp, 1896 – “PRIM” (Egorov et al. 1996).*malignus* (Faust, 1887) – KHAB, PRIM.=*filicornis* Reitter, 1915=*longulus* Egorov et Zherichin, 1991**Genus *Myllocerus* Schoenherr, 1823****Subgenus *Myllocerus* s. str.***raddensis* Pic, 1904 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.**Genus *Myosides* Roelofs, 1873***seriehispidus* Roelofs, 1873 – PRIM.**Genus *Nothomyllocerus* Kojima et Morimoto, 2006***griseus* (Roelofs, 1973) – “KUR” (Egorov et al. 1996).*illitus* (Reitter, 1915) – PRIM.**Genus *Phyllolytus* Fairmaire, 1889***variabilis* (Roelofs, 1873) – PRIM.**Genus *Ptochus* Schoenherr, 1826***impressicollis* Faust, 1881 – KHA, TUV.*nebulosus* Egorov et Zherichin, 1991 – PRIM.*porcellus* Boheman, 1834 – OMS, “ALT” (Heyden 1880-1881).

Insertae sedis

rufipes Gebler, 1829 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).**Genus *Sphaeroptochus* Egorov et Zherichin, 1991***fasciolatus* (Gebler, 1829) – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR.=*deportatus* Boheman, 1834*tristis* Egorov et Zherichin, 1991 – PRIM.

Insertae sedis

strigirostris (Hochhuth, 1851) – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

Subtribe Phytoscaphina Lacordaire, 1863

Genus *Chloebius* Schoenherr, 1826

immitus Schoenherr, 1826 – NOV, ALT.

=*psittacinus* Boheman, 1842

Tribe Peritelini Lacordaire, 1863

Subtribe Peritelina Lacordaire, 1863

Genus *Centricnemus* Germar, 1827

leucogrammus (Germar, 1823) – TMN, CHEL, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT.

Genus *Peritelus* Germar, 1823

[*sphaeroides* Germar, 1823 – “Siberia” (Winkler 1930-1932)].

Tribe Omiini Shuckard, 1840

Genus *Asphalmus* Sharp, 1896

japonicus Sharp, 1896 – KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Omius* Germar, 1817

globulus (Boheman, 1842) – IRK.

murinus (Boheman, 1842) – KURG.

puberulus Boheman, 1834 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, NOV, ALT, TUV.

=*rotundatus* (Fabricius, 1792)

verruca Boheman, 1834 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, NOV, ALT.

Genus *Yunakovius* Borovec, 2010

orientalis Borovec, 2010 – IRK, CHT, KHAB, PRIM.

Tribe Sciaphilini Sharp, 1891

Genus *Archeophloeus* Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1959

inermis (Boheman, 1842) – NOV.

Genus *Brachysomus* Schoenherr, 1823

Subgenus *Brachysomus* s. str.

echinatus (Bonsdorff, 1785) – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA,

KRN, IRK, BUR, PRIM.

Genus *Cathormiocerus* Schoenherr, 1842

aristatus (Gyllenhal, 1827) – TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, KRN, IRK, BUR.

Genus *Eudipnus* Thomson, 1859

mollis (Strom, 1768) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, BUR, YAK.

Genus *Eusomatus* Krynicki, 1834

claviger (Schilsky, 1912) – “PRIM” (Egorov 1976b).
obovatus (Boheman, 1840) – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KHA.
virens (Boheman, 1833) – “ALT” (Heyden 1880-1881).

Genus *Eusomostrophus* Tournier, 1878

acuminatus (Boheman, 1840) – CHEL, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT.

Genus *Eusomus* Germar, 1823

ovulum Germar, 1823 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, IRK.

Genus *Foucartia* Jacquelin du Val, 1854

squamulata (Herbst, 1795) – TMN, CHEL, NOV, KEM, ALT.

Genus *Sciaphilus* Schoenherr, 1824

asperatus (Bonsdorff, 1875) – TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, ALT, SAKH.

Genus *Sciaphobus* K. Daniel, 1904**Subgenus *Neosciaphobus* Apfelbeck, 1922**

ningnidus (Germar, 1823) – CHEL.
 =*rubi* Gyllenhal, 1813

Tribe Trachyphloeini Lacordaire, 1863**Subtribe Trachyphloeina Lacordaire, 1863****Genus *Trachyphloeus* Germar, 1817****Subgenus *Trachyphloeus* s. str.**

heymesii Huberthal, 1934 – TMN, NOV.
spinimanus Germar, 1823 – CHEL, KURG, OMS, NOV, ALT.

Genus *Romualdius* Borovec, 2009

scaber (Linnaeus, 1758) – TOM.
 =*bifoveolatus* Beck, 1817

Subtribe Trachyphilina Voss, 1948

Genus *Trachyphilus* Faust, 1887

saluber Faust, 1887 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

sordidus Sharp, 1890 – KUR.

Subtribe Pseudocneorrhinina Kono, 1930

Genus *Pseudocneorhinus* Roelofs, 1873

[*biasciatus* Roelofs, 1879 – “PRIM” (Legalov 2010a)].

[*minimus* Roelofs, 1879 – “PRIM” (Legalov 2010a)].

obesus Roelofs, 1873 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, KUR.

setosus Roelofs, 1879 – PRIM.

Supertribe Polydrusitae Schoenherr, 1823

Tribe Sitonini Gistel, 1856

Genus *Sitona* Germar, 1817

aberans Faust, 1887 – KHAB, PRIM.

ambiguus Gyllenhal, 1834 – KHM, TMN, CHEL, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, IRK.

amurensis Faust, 1882 – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

argenteomontanus Korotyaev, 1979 – TUV.

borealis Korotyaev, 1979 – KRN, YAK, CHUK, MAG.

callosus Gyllenhal, 1834 – TMN, KURG, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT,

cylindricollis cylindricollis Fahraeus, 1840 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

hispidulus (Fabricius, 1777) – OMS, NOV.

humeralis (Stephens, 1831) – “ALT” (Heyden 1880-1881).

inops Gyllenhal, 1832 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT.

lateralis Gyllenhal, 1834 – KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, YAK,

obsoletus obsoletus (Gmelin, 1790) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

lineatus (Linnaeus, 1758) – KHM, TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, IRK.

lineellus (Bonsdorff, 1785) – KHM, TMN, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, CHUK, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

longulus Gyllenhal, 1834 – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL.

lukjanovitshi Egorov et Korotyaev, 1986 – AMUR, PRIM.

macularius (Marsham, 1802) – TMN, CHEL, KURG.

obscuratus Faust, 1882 – TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KHA, IRK, YAK.

onerosus Faust, 1890 – OMS, NOV, RAL, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT.

ovipennis Hochhut, 1851 – TOM, NOV, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

ponomarenkoi Korotyaev, 1995 – ALT.

simillimus Korotyaev, 1979 – KHAB, PRIM.

striatellus Gyllenhal, 1834 – CHEL.

sulcifrons sulcifrons (Thunberg, 1798) – TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, KHAB, PRIM.

suturalis Stephens, 1831 – KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

tesselatus Korotyaev, 1979 – BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

[*versicolor* Faust, 1887 – “IRK” (Berlov and Tomilova 1980).

Incertae sedis

costatus Fischer de Faldheim, 1842 – “Sib. oc.” (Petrukha 1969), “Sib. or.” (Winkler 1930-1932).

Genus *Velazquezia* Alonso-Zarazaga et Lyal, 1999

[*akini* (Faust, 1885) – RAL].

Tribe Naupactini Gistel, 1856

Subtribe Mesagroicina Legalov, 2020

Genus *Mesagroicus* Schoenherr, 1840

angustirostris Faust, 1882 – CHT, AMUR, PRIM.

piliferus (Boheman, 1833) – ALT.

Tribe Polydrusini Schoenherr, 1823

Genus *Liophloeus* Germar, 1823

Subgenus *Liophloeus* s. str.

[*tessulatus* (Muller, 1776) – “Siberia” (Heyden 1880-1881)].

Genus *Polydrusus* Germar, 1817

Subgenus *Caenotylodrosus* Kôno et Morimoto, 1960

obesulus Faust, 1882 – CHT, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Subgenus *Chlorodrosus* Daniel et Daniel, 1898

amoenus (Germar, 1823) – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, IRK, BUR, AMUR.

Subgenus *Eurodrusus* Korotyaev et Meleshko, 1997

cervinus (Linnaeus, 1758) – CHEL, ALT.

pilosus Gredler, 1866 – KHM, TMN, CHEL, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, IRK, BUR, CHT, AMUR.

Subgenus *Eustolus* Thomson, 1859

corruscus Germar, 1823 – TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, CHT, BUR, AMUR, PRIM.

= *kirgisicus* Csiki, 1922

flavipes flavipes (Degeer, 1775) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, CHT, AMUR, Khab, PRIM.

pterygomalis Boheman, 1840 – TMN, NOV, KEM, ALT, “Wladivostok” (Dieckmann 1980).

Subgenus *Leucodrusus* Stierlin, 1884

[*mariae* (Faust, 1882) – “Irkutsk” (Winkler 1930-1932)].

Subgenus *Polydrusus* s. str.

fulvicornis fulvicornis (Fabricius, 1792) – YAN, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, IRK, BUR, YAK, AMUR, Khab, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

tereticollis (DeGeer, 1775) – KHM, TMN, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, YAK, PRIM.

Subgenus *Thomsononymus* Desbrochers des Loges, 1902

[*formosus* (Mayer, 1779) – “Siberia” (Dieckmann 1980)]

= *sericeus* Shaller, 1783

Subgenus *Scythodrusus* Korotyaev et Meleschko, 1997

inustus Germar, 1823 – NOV, KEM, ALT.

Genus *Paophilus* Faust, 1891

albilaterus (Faust, 1882) – TOM, NOV, KEM, RAL, KHA, TUV.

hispidus (Faust, 1882) – KHA.

Tribe Brachyderini Schoenherr, 1826

Genus *Achradidius* Kiesenwetter, 1864

theresae (Pic, 1910) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

Genus *Pholicodes* Schoenherr, 1826

Subgenus *Pholicodes* s. str.

inauratus inauratus Boheman, 1833 – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, YAK.

[*lepidopterus* Boheman, 1839 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

Genus *Strophosoma* Billberg, 1820**Subgenus *Pelletierius* Alonso-Zarazaga et Lyal, 1999**

albosignatus (Boheman, 1840) – KURG.

Subgenus *Strophosoma* s. str.

capitatum (Degeer, 1775) – TMN, KURG, TOM, NOV.

[*melanogrammum melanogrammum* (Forster, 1771) – “YAK” (Averensky 2003b)].

Tribe Blosyrini Lacordaire, 1863**Genus *Blosyrus* Schoenherr, 1823**

falcatus (Faust, 1882) – IRK, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

=*japonicus* Sharp, 1896

Genus *Dactylotus* Schoenherr, 1847**Subgenus *Dactylotinus* Korotyaev, 1996**

globosus (Gebler, 1829) – YAN, KHM, TOM, KEM, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK.

orientalis Korotyaev et Egorov, 1992 – KHAB, PRIM.

tshuktsha Lukjanovich, 1992 – YAK, CHUK, MAG.

Subgenus *Dactylotus* s. str.

sedakoffi Schoenherr, 1847 – BUR, CHT.

Tribe Cneorhinini Lacordaire, 1863**Genus *Callirhopalus* Hochhut, 1851**

sedakowii Hochhut, 1851 – KRN, KHA, IRK, BUR, CHT.

Genus *Catapionus* Schoenherr, 1842

[*ballioni* Heyden, 1880 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

gracilicornis gracilicornis Roelofs, 1873 – SAKH, KUR.

gracilicornis obscurus Sharp, 1896 – KHAB, PRIM.

fossulatus Motschulsky, 1860 – KHAB, PRIM.

[*intermedius* Tournier, 1875 – “Eastern Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

quadrilineatus (Gebler, 1829) – TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL.

[*rugosicollis* Desbrochers des Loges, 1870 – “Siberia” (Heyden 1880-1881)].

[*viridanus* Tournier, 1875 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017)].

viridimetallicus Motschulsky, 1860 – SAKH, KUR.

Insertae sedis

argentatus (Gebler, 1829) – “Altai” (Emden M. and Emden F. 1939).

gebleri Faust, 1883 – “Daurien” (Emden M. and Emden F. 1939).
globosus (Boheman, 1833) – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).

Tribe Tanymecini Lacordaire, 1863

Subtribe Tanymecina Lacordaire, 1863

Genus *Chlorophanus* C. Sahlberg, 1823

micans Krynicki, 1832 – “Western Siberia” (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017).
mordkovitshi Legalov, 1998 – TUV.
rufomarginatus Gebler, 1829 – ALT.
schoenherri Faust, 1897 – BUR, CHT.
sellatus (Fabricius, 1798) – TMN, KURG, TMN, OMS.
sibiricus Gyllenhal, 1834 – YAN, KHM, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHA, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
=*grandis* Roelofs, 1873
[*simulans* Faust, 1897 – “Siberia” (Günter and Zumpt 1933; Voss 1955).
tuvensis Korotyaev, 1992 – TUV.
viridis viridis (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN.
[*vittatus* Menetries, 1832 – “Transbaicalia (?)” (Korotyaev 1992b).

Genus *Cycloderes* C. Sahlberg, 1823

pilosulus (Herbst, 1795) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, KHA, TUV, IRK, BUR.

Genus *Diglossotrox* Lacordaire, 1863

mannerheimi Lacordaire, 1863 – BUR.

Genus *Megamecus* Reitter, 1903

Subgenus *Acercomecus* Reitter, 1903

bidentatus (Gebler, 1829), **comb. nov.** – TMN, CHEL, NOV, ALT, TUV.
=*argentatus* Gyllenhal, 1840, **syn. nov.**

Subgenus *Megamecus* s. str.

variegatus (Gebler, 1829) – TMN, [record of this species from “Siberien” (Günter and Zumpt, 1933) belongs to Kazakhstan].

Genus *Leptomias* Faust, 1886

humilis (Faust, 1882) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.
schoenherri (Faust, 1882) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Meotiorhynchus* Sharp, 1896

querendus Sharp, 1896 – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Mythecops* Reitter, 1916

[*gracilipes* (Faust, 1881) – record of this species from “Siberia” (Winkler 1930-1932) belongs to Kazakhstan].

Genus *Phacephorus* Schoenherr, 1840

nebulosus Fanraeus, 1840 – TMN, NOV, ALT, CHT.

sibiricus Gyllenhal, 1840 – NOV, KEM, ALT, BUR, CHT.

umbratus (Falderman, 1835) – RAL, TUV, BUR.

vilis Fahraeus, 1840 – CHT.

Genus *Protenomus* Schoenherr, 1826

[*saisanensis* Schoenherr, 1826 – record of this species from “Altai” (Günter and Zumpt 1933) belongs to East-Kazakhstan Prov.].

Genus *Scepticus* Roelofs, 1873

fausti Guenter, 1933 – “SAKH” (Günter and Zumpt 1933).

insularis Roelofs, 1873 – “SAKH” (Morimoto 1962b).

tigrinus Roelofs, 1873 – “SAKH, KUR” (Egorov and Basarukina 1981).

Genus *Tanymecus* Germar, 1817**Subgenus *Tanymecus* s. str.**

palliatius (Fabricius, 1787) – TMN, CHEL, KURG, OMS, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, KRN, IRK, BUR, YAK.

Subtribe *Piazomina* Reitter, 1913**Genus *Meteutinopus* Zumpt, 1931**

mongolicus (Faust, 1881) – BUR, CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

mus (Faust, 1888) – “Baical” (Winkler 1930-1932).

Genus *Piazomias* Schoenherr, 1840

[*baeckmanni* Suvorov, 1915 – “Sibirien” (Günter and Zumpt 1933)].

semenovi Suvorov, 1915 – NOV.

virescens Boheman, 1839 – BUR, CHT, KHAB.

Genus *Sympiezomias* Faust, 1887

lewisii lewisii Roelofs, 1879 – “KUR (?)” (Krivolutskaja et al. 1978).

Subtribe *Tainophthalmina* Desbrochers des Loges, 1873**Genus *Amystax* Roelofs, 1873**

fasciatus Roelofs, 1873 – KUR.

Currently, 1464 species of Curculionid beetles (Nemonychidae – 1, Anthribidae – 76, Rhynchitidae – 78, Attelabidae – 28, Brentidae – 131 and Curculionidae – 1150) are recorded from Siberia and the Russian Far East. Forty species are found in Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Okrug, 84 species in Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug, 313 species in Tyumen Oblast, 182 species in Chelyabinsk Oblast, 129 species in Kurgan Oblast, 172 species in Omsk Oblast, 299 species in Tomsk Oblast, 439 species in Novosibirsk Oblast, 324 species in Kemerovo Oblast, 356 species in Altay Krai, 296 species in Altai Republic, 182 species in Krasnoyarsk Krai, 114 species in Republic of Khakassia, 244 species in Tyva Republic, 283 species in Irkutsk Oblast, 239 species in Buryatiya Republic, 286 species in Zabaikalskii Krai, 153 species in Sakha (Yakutia) Republic, 74 species in Far East: Kamchatka Oblast, 43 species in Chukotka Autonomous Okrug, 105 species in Magadan Oblast, 325 species in Amur Oblast, 312 species in Khabarovsk Krai, 599 species in Primorsky Krai, 225 species in Sakhalin Is. and 218 species in Kuriles Isl. 112 species are excluded from the fauna of Siberia and the Russian Far East.

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